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Summary

The Equal-Life project aims to investigate the combined effects of various exposures on children and adolescent mental health across different developmental stages. Important to this project is the collaboration with stakeholders.

The task “Connecting science to policy” related to D8.2 has the objective to establish a bi-directional dialogue between the Equal-Life project and (inter)national policy makers to 1) translate project results into effective children health policies and 2) inject knowledge about best practices and health policies into the project.

This deliverable is a report of meetings with stakeholders representing the dialogues with those stakeholders. There were nine different meetings. Each meeting was structured according to different themes. The world café sessions were targeted to collect information from the stakeholders to create a science-policy interface. The stakeholder fora in Ljubljana, Milano and in Helsinki were structured according to different interactive sessions. Different working methods were used. A range of potential outcomes were addressed.

The outcomes of the world café sessions, the co-design workshops and stakeholder fora signify a major step toward developing a set of policy implementations, a toolbox and guidebook. These outcomes not only address the complexities of exposome data but also ensures its practical applicability in diverse settings. The collaborative and inclusive nature of this effort reflects a commitment to advancing our understanding of the exposome's impact on child mental health and cognitive development. The findings provide a foundation for informed policy decisions, promoting the integration of this toolbox into relevant research, healthcare, and educational initiatives.

The collected information from stakeholders contributes to get into an interactive mode with stakeholders. They are interested in practical implications of Equal-Life results. It should assist the stakeholders to understand the connections between the multiple results displayed and what they mean for options of interventions. For the scientific community, nearness to decision-makers is important. Scientists should make use of communication experts were applicable in order to communicate their data results and recommendations.

1 Introduction

The task “Connecting science to policy ” related to D8.2 has the objective to establish a bi-directional dialogue between the Equal-Life project and (inter)national policy makers to 1) translate project results into effective children health policies and 2) inject knowledge about best practices and health policies into the project. This task ensures that the generated knowledge (on exposome, mechanisms, and health effects) is developed in line with the needs of the broader society, and that knowledge of the involved (public and private) stakeholders will help to interpret the results. This science-policy interaction gives a better understanding of the societal impact and relevance of the Equal-Life research both for the scientists within the project as for the stakeholders. We have identified key stakeholder (policy makers, regulators and research networks), and set up two formal co-design workshop and three stakeholder fora and established regular interaction between scientists and stakeholders.

This deliverable is in a format of a report. It is a representation of all activities in nine different meetings. Each meeting was structured according to different themes. The stakeholder fora in Ljubljana, Milano and in Helsinki were structured according to different interactive sessions.

- World café sessions in 2021 and 2022
- Stakeholder forum in Ljubljana, March 7 - 8, 2022
- Co-design workshop in Skopje, September 14 -15, 2022
- Stakeholder forum in Milan, November 16 -17, 2022
- Co-design workshop in Como, June 29-30, 2023
- Stakeholder forum in Helsinki September 7-8, 2023

This report reflects only the minutes of the meetings There is an overlap with D8.4. This report shows more on the presentations and less on the conclusions of the interaction with the stakeholders. This since in the project proposal there was not made a clear distinction between the meetings that were meant to be only to communicate with stakeholders or to be meant for interaction. Only the world café sessions during the first project could be recognized as a purely dialogue process.

The Deliverable 8.2 will be updated again in 2024 after upcoming meetings with stakeholders.

World café session

The World Café methodology is a simple, effective, and flexible format for conducting a group dialogue. Each element of the method has a specific purpose and corresponds to one or more of the design principles. The method makes use of an informal cafe setting for participants to explore an issue by discussing it in small table groups. Discussion is held in multiple rounds of 20-30 minutes, with the cafe ambiance intended to allow for more relaxed and open conversations to take place. It is a method to quickly collect a lot of information as all participants have the opportunity to speak.

Co-design workshop

Co-design is the act of creating interaction with stakeholders (policymakers, end-users) specifically within a design development process to ensure that the results meet their needs and are usable. Its aim is to create something not only for people, but also with them. Stakeholders can become creators of a product being actively involved in the creation process. Co-design is often a transdisciplinary

process. The result can be a report or a product (handbook, guideline). In Equal-Life the co-design is a tool to enable stakeholders to use Equal-Life results for policy making or even to draft interventions. We conducted one co-design workshop in Skopje (see chapter 3).

Stakeholder forum

Stakeholder Forum means a platform open to representatives of institutions, national, regional and local authorities, organised interests and individual entities from different domains, higher education, research, associations, civil society and cluster organisations, as well as other interested parties from across a selected knowledge or policy focus.

The setup of the work process of co-design workshops or stakeholder forum is similar. The forum aims more at sending information between the participants. The co-design workshop aims at producing content related to the products that are seen as result of the project.

The process of the co-design workshop and stakeholder forum uses a structured approach. This approach facilitates a codesign workshop/forum aimed at collaboratively developing 1) input for policy recommendations; 2) a tool or guidebook with support from diverse stakeholders. The process emphasizes open communication, active participation, and iterative feedback to ensure a well-rounded and inclusive final product. The following steps can be identified and have been used at the different workshops and fora.

1. **Defining Objectives and Scope:** The workshop begins with a clear articulation of its purpose and goals. The focus is on defining the scope of the tool or guidebook, establishing boundaries to guide the collaborative process.
2. **Identifying Stakeholders:** Stakeholders, including end-users, subject matter experts, and decision-makers, are identified and invited to participate. The goal is to ensure a diverse representation that captures a broad range of perspectives.
3. **Pre-workshop Preparation:** Participants receive relevant information before the workshop, along with materials or resources to review. A communication platform is established to facilitate ongoing collaboration among stakeholders.
4. **Workshop Agenda:** A detailed agenda outlines the workshop activities, incorporating introductions, icebreakers, and specific design sessions. Time is allocated for brainstorming, prototyping, and feedback sessions.
5. **Facilitation Techniques:** Facilitation techniques are employed to encourage open communication, active participation, and equal contribution. The facilitator fosters a collaborative and inclusive environment where all voices are heard.
6. **Brainstorming:** Structured brainstorming sessions are conducted to generate ideas. Techniques such as mind mapping or affinity diagrams are employed, and participants are encouraged to share their perspectives and insights.
7. **Prototyping:** The design is broken down into smaller components, and participants work on creating prototypes or drafts of the tool or guidebook. Collaborative tools or physical materials are used to visualize ideas.
8. **Iterative Feedback:** Regular feedback sessions are facilitated, allowing stakeholders to review and provide input on prototypes. Constructive criticism is encouraged, and concerns are addressed to refine the design.

9. Decision-Making: Facilitated decision-making sessions help prioritize features, content, or design elements. Techniques like dot voting or consensus building are used to reach agreements among stakeholders.

10. Documentation: Outcomes, decisions, and changes made during the workshop are thoroughly documented. A roadmap or action plan will create for the next steps in the development process.

11. Follow-up and Implementation: Stakeholders are kept informed about the workshop outcomes. Agreed-upon design changes are implemented, and stakeholders are continuously involved in the development process.

12. Communication: Ongoing communication is maintained with stakeholders throughout the development process. Regular updates and involvement in future iterations ensure sustained collaboration.

By following these steps, the codesign process became a dynamic and inclusive journey, harnessing the collective creativity and expertise of stakeholders to develop a valuable and well-received steps towards policy implications, a tool or guidebook.

The following sections describe the different sessions that were organised with stakeholders.

2 World Café session

2.1 Two online world café sessions January and February 2021

Method: An online World-Café was hosted to create a science-policy interface for South-Eastern European stakeholders with relevant backgrounds to environmental research and/or children's (mental) health. Via qualitative content analysis methods, the data retrieved from the 7 participating stakeholders was thematically analysed and coded.

Results: The stakeholders increasingly shared, both beneficial and harmful, internal exposures (e.g. metabolism, microbiome, melatonin system, parents age), physical exposures (e.g. outdoor green-, blue- and edible-space and playgrounds; urban versus rural living; quality of indoor and outdoor space including air pollution and noise; lifestyle factors such as physical activity, diet and school performance medication intake) and social exposures (e.g. a variety of social contacts and their characteristics including peers and parents; the age of parents at birth in Romania; screen time and living a sedentary lifestyle; family/work-life (im-)balance; bicycling lifestyle; competitiveness and awareness around mental health in South-Eastern Europe; socioeconomic circumstances and access to services; institutionalisation in Bulgaria; COVID measures and other legislations and priorities of the government). Mental health outcomes were described through emotional status and mediating factors with caution for diagnosing children. Age periods discussed were prenatal, early age and adolescence.

Conclusion: Southeastern European stakeholder involvement can be facilitated within a science-policy interface, is appreciated and contributes to specific country-based topics. Within the wide range of internal and external exposures shared by the stakeholders, social exposures appear to be the main field of concern. While talking about exposures, clustering of multiple exposures often develops naturally. To benefit children's mental health and cognitive development a plea for country specific legislations following research outcomes was made, preferably with a focus on preventive and

beneficial measures. Further evaluation on including exposure to COVID measures and exposure to the microbiome is recommended and a change in the look upon life success can be examined. Furthermore, to benefit children's mental health, exposome research and the environment, usage of the digital lifestyle is suggested and additional involvement of children in general.

A summary of the results is in Annex 1.

2.2 World café 18 May 2021

There were four participants at the online session. They were from different Southeastern European countries.

Three questions were addressed in this session.

- 1) The internal, external and social exposures you consider as potentially harmful to children's mental health and cognitive development.
- 2) The internal, external and social exposures that you consider as potentially beneficial to children's mental health and cognitive development.
- 3) The mental health problems and cognitive developmental disorders in children that you observe being affected by all exposures and the children affected by these exposures.

The dialogue with the participants can be found in annex 2.

2.3 World café 17 June 2021 – Dutch stakeholders

There were three participants at the online session. They were from the Netherlands.

Three themes were addressed in this session.

Theme1 - The internal, external and social exposures you consider as potentially harmful to children's mental health and cognitive development.

Theme 2 – The internal, external and social exposures that you consider as potentially beneficial to children's mental health and cognitive development.

Theme 3 – The mental health problems and cognitive developmental disorders in children that you observe being affected by all exposures and the children affected by these exposures.

The dialogue with the participants can be found in annex 2.

3 Stakeholder forum Ljubljana

This section describes the activities of the stakeholder forum and the presentations that took place in Ljubljana in March 2022.

About 25 people were present in the sessions, in addition to approximately 20 people online. Among the 25 live attendees were people from Slovenia, Croatia, Finland, Italy, and the Netherlands. Persons from Greece, Sweden, Slovakia, North Macedonia, and Germany were also present online. The group was about 50-50 divided between people who are focused in their work on public (mental) health and people who are focused on the physical environment. From the Equal-Life project, several researchers from different countries and institutes joined as well.

The session consisted of three themes. Each theme was briefly introduced with several questions, using the program Mentimeter. The participants were divided into groups (multiple groups in-person and online) and discussed the themes with each other. The group conversations were plenary reported back to the entire group. The results of the Mentimeter questions can be found in Annex 4.

The description of the dialogue with the stakeholders on the different themes is in annex 5.

4 Co-design workshop Skopje

A co-design workshop in Skopje, North Macedonia was held on the 14th and 15th of September 2022. This workshop discussed the progress and interaction with stakeholders in the Equal-Life project. But also, about the best ways of using the expected Equal-Life project results for implementing policies or interventions. What tools are available? How to best design policies? What are your needs as stakeholders working in the domain of children's mental health, cognitive development or protecting the social or physical environment? How can science and civil society organisations best cooperate?

The workshop was a live workshop. A total of 19 persons attended. The workshop took place at the Holiday Inn hotel in Skopje, North Macedonia.

The workshop was structured according to different themes. Each theme was introduced by one of the Equal-Life partners.

We used descriptions of personas of different kind of stakeholders in the workshop. The purpose of personas is to create reliable and realistic representations of a key audience. These representations should be based on qualitative and some quantitative user research. We wanted to get some insight of what kind of stakeholders are relevant for cooperation with researchers within the Equal-Life project. Not all possible stakeholders were present. The knowledge of which stakeholders were not present is also relevant information. We must consider how to reach out to those missing stakeholders. Some examples of the different personas that have been developed by the participants are added in the annex 6.

See for details on the work with stakeholders annex 7.

5 Stakeholder forum Milano

The Milan stakeholder forum aimed to bring together professionals in the domains of mental health and environmental health to discuss 1) exposure to the physical and social environment of children; 2) the use of tools as a strategy to bridge the science and policy domain; and 3) using the future Equal-Life project results for implementing policies or interventions to improve children's environments and

mental health. 17 stakeholders were (part-time) present, together with 23 researchers (5 of them online) from the Equal-Life project.

The forum took place November 16-17, 2022, at the Starhotel Ritz in Milan, Italy. The first day was dedicated to presentations on work from Equal-Life researchers and stakeholders, followed by world café discussions. The first day was closed with a workshop on the logic model that is developed within Equal-Life as a tool to encourage thinking about social inequalities in urban planning interventions.

The second day opened with a workshop on how to evaluate children's access to public outdoor play space, research that is also performed within Equal-Life. The rest of the day was dedicated to discussing policy recommendations and useful interventions in the environmental mental health domain.

The hands-on workshops provided the Equal-Life project researchers with valuable input to improve the presented tools. Some conclusions:

- Stakeholders want to have a role in Equal-Life, for example in piloting Equal-Life (draft) outcomes (knowledge and tools) and in co-designing of or commenting on Equal-Life deliverables.
- Interaction with Equal-Life researchers and involvement of stakeholders in (specific) work (packages) need to be facilitated and increased, for example in (in-person) meetings as well as in one-to-one settings and online working groups.

The dialogues of this meeting are in annex 8.

6. Co-design workshop Como

A co-design workshop in Como, Italy was held on the 29th and 30th of June 2023. This workshop discussed the progress and interaction with stakeholders in the Equal-Life project. But also, about the best ways of using the expected Equal-Life project results for implementing policies or interventions. How should we design the tools? How to incorporate the generated data from Equal-Life in the design of policies? What are you the needs as stakeholders working in the domain of children's mental health, cognitive development to link Equal-Life results to the work that stakeholders do? How can science and civil society organisations best cooperate?

The dialogues of this meeting are in annex 9.

7. Stakeholder forum Helsinki

A stakeholder forum was conducted at 7 and 8 September 2023 in City Hall, Helsinki. This meeting is organized by stakeholder from the City of Helsinki. There were 14 stakeholders present and 14 representatives of the Equal-Life project.

The aim of the meeting was to give input towards the way towards development of policy recommendations, towards the content of the toolbox and good practices/requirements for training to implement policy recommendations and tools.

The dialogues of this meeting are in annex 10.

8. Partners / Equal-Life contact information

22 Partners

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9. Annexes

Annex 1 Two online world café sessions January and February 2021

Results

All the stakeholders stated that they had not heard of the exposome concept before they were contacted by us to be part of the World Café conversations. The following internal, physical and social exposures were identified by the stakeholders as potentially harmful and/or beneficial, alongside the mental health and cognitive development outcomes and age categories that they found to be of importance in upcoming research (Table 3, 4, 5 and 6). The results within the following text are arranged utmost by exposome components and in order of importance according to the stakeholders without detracting from the stakeholder's opinion. Bold and cursive words correspond with the codes presented in the tables. References accompanying results were specifically presented by the stakeholders.

Internal	Physical	Social
Metabolism (<i>sedentary lifestyle, diet</i>)	Air pollution (<i>volatile compounds, urban/rural living, car use, burning solids</i>)	Social contacts (<i>abuse, sexual exploitation, violence</i>)
- Oxidative stress	Outdoor space (<i>danger, blue space</i>)	- Parents (<i>age, addiction, busy</i>)
- OMICs	Plastics (<i>micro plastics, phthalate, bisphenols, bottles/ containers/packaging</i>)	- School (<i>teachers, competition</i>)
Microbiome (<i>less exposure, food intolerances anti-vaccine</i>)	Pesticides	- Peers
Screen time	Chemicals (<i>lead, uranium, ores, old pesticides</i>)	- Family
- Melatonin system	Food additives	COVID measures
Age parents (>35 years)	Cigarette smoke (<i>volatile compounds, low oxygen</i>)	Screen time (<i>internet, television, social media</i>)
	Noise	- Sedentary lifestyle
	Screen time (<i>blue light, distractive</i>)	- Lack of peer contact
	Indoor space	Lifestyle
	School performance medication	- Family/work-life imbalance
		- Indoor
		- Sedentary
		- Competitive
		Government and policies (<i>institutionalisation, incorrect diagnosing, correctional institutes</i>)
		Economic status (<i>poverty</i>)
		No access to services (<i>education, books, (mental) health care, child care, disability care</i>)
		Outdoor space (<i>danger/safety, conflict inducing</i>)
		Over diagnosing
		Overinforming

Table 3. Harmful exposures and *featuring segments* identified by the stakeholders

Internal	Physical	Social
Physical activity	Physical activity Outdoor space (<i>balance safety/danger, school, learning, creativity, cleanliness</i>) - Green space - Blue space - Edible space - Playgrounds Rural living Sound Indoor space	Social contacts (<i>unconditional love, support, feeling heard, involvement</i>) - Parents (<i>education, age</i>) - Peers (<i>sports</i>) - Teachers - Family Screen time (<i>learning, peer contact, gamification, social media</i>) Economic status Government and policies Access to services - School - (Mental) health care - Child care - Violence protection - Mediation Outdoor space (<i>peer contact</i>) Lifestyle (<i>family/work-life balance, bicycling</i>) Awareness around mental health

Table 4. Beneficial exposures and *featuring segments* identified by the stakeholders

Internalizing	Externalizing	Other	Mediating factors	Cognitive development
Emotional symptoms Anxiety Trauma Depression Suicide	Concentration problems Agitation Aggression ADHD	Anti-social behaviour Health issues Eating disorders Well-being (<i>secureness, calmness, happiness</i>)	Resilience Stress Sleep Attachment Self-image World-image	Social skills Communication skills Verbal skills (<i>vocabulary</i>) Motor skills Fine motor skills Digital skills School performance Intelligence Curiosity

Table 5. Mental health and Cognitive development outcomes identified by the stakeholders

Internal exposome: The stakeholders mentioned the **metabolism** as a possible important internal exposome component affecting children’s mental health and cognitive development. It was suggested that the high metabolic demand of the brain in early ages could be affected by *air pollution* and that the effects could be measured in the amount of **oxidative stress** or through **OMICS**. Further effects on the metabolism were suggested to be caused by children’s *diet* and the amount of *physical activity* they have but also in particular by the *sedentary lifestyle* as a consequence of an increase in the amount of time spend behind electronic screens, also known as *screen time*, in the current digital age. Aside from the upcoming sedentary lifestyle the screen time also affects the amount of *blue light* children are exposed to during daytime and during nighttime, especially when looked at teenagers, which may affect their **melatonin system** and **sleep** and therefore again also their metabolism.

Another internal exposome component the stakeholders mentioned was the **microbiome**. The rise in the *anti-vaccine movement* during the last decades is noticed, a *lack of exposure* and an increase in parents and children with *food intolerances*. These phenomena are all related to the microbiome and could have possible effects on children’s development.

Physical exposome: The stakeholders reported the **outdoor space**, and all it comprises, as a beneficial but sometimes also harmful part of the physical and social exposome. It was said there has been a lot of research on the beneficial effects of outdoor space on children’s mental health and the importance of creating outdoor places not only close to children’s living environments and neighbourhoods but also near kindergartens and schools. The outdoor places were said to have calming effects, help children stay connected with the real world and to encourage *peer contact*. There were multiple requirements brought up by the stakeholders to meet the conditions of the outdoor space to be stimulating for the mental health and cognitive development such as *stimulating to learn* which can be done through play, but also by involving children in preserving the outdoor space; *encouraging discovery through all senses*; *stimulating creativity* and imagination; *cleanliness* and *maintenance*; to be able to be alone or to share the space and the right *balance between danger and safety*, all potentially benefitting children’s **motor skills**, **curiosity** and **world-image**. Concerning safety, it was said to be necessary to distinguish between the safety of play and the

Age categories

Prenatal
Early age
Teenagers

Table 6. Age Categories identified by the stakeholders

safety of the accessibility but also the importance of not too much safety to keep a challenge which stimulates development.ⁱ

The stakeholders defined multiple components that the beneficial outdoor space could comprise of: **Green space** which can range from parks to actively planting trees; but also specifically include **edible space**, green space that is being grown to eat, near children's living environments and school environment. **Blue space** comprising of lakes, rivers and the possibility to swim and **playgrounds** to stimulate the cognitive development of children.

The stakeholders mentioned the outdoor space becoming a harmful exposure when it is too *dangerous* or (*peer*) *conflict inducing* which can make children feel less welcome and safe. This for example happens when there is not enough space, when space is *poorly maintained* or comprising of *toxins*; toxins in the blue space in particular, because blue spaces are often not designed with children in mind. Harmful outdoor spaces were reported to be seen in areas accommodating more immigrants and having higher poverty rates.

Stakeholders specifically pointed out **sound** to be both a possible harmful and beneficial exposure within the outdoor space and the **indoor space** by giving a different feeling to inside and outside environments. Harmful sound is referred to as **noise** and is being seen as disturbing, especially for small children who are not able to say anything about the noise. Contrarily, sound could also be beneficial, giving examples of nature sounds or music. Noise was said to affect **school performance**, to potentially cause **concentration**, **agitation** and sometimes even **aggression** problems. According to the stakeholders, the WHO already has particularly good guidelines for noise but due to a lack of legislation they are not being implemented.

Almost every stakeholder mentioned the widespread problem of **air pollution** affecting everyone from the moment of conception onwards and pointing out the need of research of the possible effects air pollution has on the mental health and cognitive development of children. Suggesting using wearable devices to measure the *volatile compounds* such as NO and O₃ people are really exposed to and as mentioned before, could have an effect on the oxidative stress and OMICS in children.

The stakeholders put forward an extra dimension to the topic of air pollution and the behaviour of people as a reaction to it. A difference has been noticed in cognitive development between children who were raised in *urban* areas compared to *rural* areas. Stating that children of the generation brought up after the second world war were sometimes separated. Those who were raised in urban areas with higher educational opportunities and better schooling still performed less **emotionally** and in terms of **school performance**, **communication skills** and **verbal skills** compared to their siblings raised in rural areas with fewer facilities but also less air pollution. Evolving through time people, often of a higher economic class, are now choosing to move outside of the metropolitan cities to greener less polluted areas turning things upside down especially during wintertime when there appears to be a rise in burning of *solid matters* such as *biomass*, *wood*, *coal* and *trash* for heating purposes during the cold months in rural areas with even more air pollution as a consequence opposed to what is measured in the city. Aside from burning solid matters the stakeholders also pointed out an increase in car use. Parents are using their cars more to cross bigger distances but also because they want to protect their children from being outside in the polluted air while going to school. As a result, children are getting out of the car, with running engines, when they reach school stepping into an extra polluted car park with more cars. A lifestyle change towards **bicycling** is suggested to be encouraged as part of solving the car use problem but even as being a potentially beneficial exposure for children on its own.

The stakeholders also mentioned **physical activity** in general as a proven beneficial exposure to

children's mental health and cognitive development by improving **emotional symptoms** and **motor skills**. The WHO has already defined the amount of time needed for physical activity in school per age category and the importance of a variety of different activities.

Stakeholders mentioned **plastic** as a potential harmful physical exposure, pointing out the dangers of *micro-plastics*, *phthalate* and *bisphenol* that could potentially harm children even before they are born. They saw the use and waste of *plastic bottles*, *(food) packaging* and *containers* as a problem. It was also said that even though countries appear to be more in control of the problem, danger is always close with new products coming onto the market every day.

Other potentially harmful elements of the physical exposome mentioned by the stakeholders were: **Cigarette smoke** and smoking by parents, often very young women, which is stated to be a widespread problem in the Balkan area and Hungary. This causes (prenatal) *oxygen deprivation* and exposes children to harmful *volatile compounds* in the smoke; **Pesticides** on food, even having prenatal effects; **Food additives** and the shortcoming incorrect labelling of food in some of the countries making it impossible to address the issue in a scientific way; **Chemicals** such as *lead*, *uranium*, *ores* coming from old mining locations and the storage of *old pesticides* which were used during the old socialist regime and still need to be taken care of safely.

Social exposome: All the stakeholders distinguished **social contacts** as potentially harmful or beneficial exposures. When *abuse*, *sexual exploitation* or *violence* occur in social contacts the development of mental health and cognitive development problems is prone to happen. On the other hand, stakeholders mentioned *unconditional love*, *support*, *feeling heard*, *involvement* in social contacts and participation in public life as potentially beneficial to children's mental health and cognitive development. "Within the interaction with other people and group dynamics children are able to learn social behaviour." The stakeholders repeatedly pointed out that **COVID measures** put in place by the government are affecting all the types of social contact by minimizing the potentially beneficial effects and enlarging the negative.

The attachment to and the relationship with **parents** in the first place, but also with **family**, were said to be proven to be of significant importance for children's mental health and cognitive developmentⁱⁱ and a parent and family strengthening approach to be the base of all child support. Parents struggling with *addiction*, *busy* parents and a family that has a **family/work-life imbalance** could harm children's mental health and cognitive development, while having a supportive family with a **family/work-life balance** could benefit the children. Stakeholders suggested that the sentiment that life's value is created through work needs to change, promoting a reduction in the number of hours spent on work, which would make it possible to spend more quality time with family.ⁱⁱⁱ Stakeholders also said that the *education* of parents could have an effect on children's cognitive development. The stakeholders specifically pointed out the *age* of the parents and its effect on children. Where Romania has a very high rate of young mothers who have their first child under 18 it also has a high rate of mothers who are having their first child after the age of **35 years** with the help of in vitro fertilisation. This results in a u-shaped birth graphic. The age of the parents could have genomic effects but more importantly, it affects the emotional and cultural environment children are brought up in. Having old parents was described as growing up with a 'grandparents-feeling', providing a more emotionally safe and stable environment with less **stress**, more bonding and better communication making children more **resilient** and giving them an advantage in cognitive development by stimulating their **communication skills**. Whereas very young mothers were said to often come from rural areas, unprivileged families and gypsy communities with less financial means, giving children a less stable environment and therefore potentially harming their development.

The stakeholders mentioned **school**, educational systems and the social contact children have with their **teachers** as both potentially harmful and beneficial exposures. The common educational system that revolves around points, grades and *competition* were said to pressure children and cause **stress**. According to the stakeholder's competition has become one of the highest values in society. They state competitiveness to be especially high amongst South-Eastern Europeans, provoking a **competitive lifestyle** which in turn causes a rise in **over diagnosing** and the use of **school performance medication** as a potentially harmful exposure on its own. Strict educational systems where, for example, a child is not allowed to use the toilet when they need to, were said to be harmful to their mental health. Online education could negatively affect their **school performance** and **social skills** by a lack of teacher and peer contact, especially the youngest children. Stakeholders pointed out that children need support from their teachers, less stress and more freedom to flourish.

The stakeholders mentioned **peer contact** to be of importance for cognitive development and mental health, with special mentioning of peer contact through *sports* improving their **social skills**. In contrast, it was said that lack of peer contact could even have a negative effect which will be further elaborated in the next section. Conflict between children was also said to be potentially related to the development of mental health problems.

Almost every stakeholder pointed out the exposure to screens as harmful, but they also saw potentially beneficial effects **screen time** can have. Screen time included the usage of *internet, television* and *social media*.

As previously mentioned, the stakeholders touched on screen time internally affecting the melatonin system through *blue light* exposure and affecting the metabolism as a consequence of the **sedentary lifestyle**. The stakeholders referred to screens as being addictive and stimulating a sedentary lifestyle at a growing rate. The sedentary lifestyle together with the **indoor lifestyle** is even further stimulated by COVID measures that are imposed by governments. It was also said that there is a rise in screen time because of busy parents and parents who use screens to control their children, reporting 18-month-old children being able to use screens.

Another concern stakeholders pointed out were children having less real-life **peer contact** because of screen time, living an indoor lifestyle and COVID measures. This makes children less able to communicate their feelings and emotions in real life and affects their **attachment, social skills, communication skills, verbal skills** and *vocabulary, self-image* and **world-image**. But in opposite screen time could also help children to learn, improve **fine motor skills** and **digital skills**, and to connect and to have fun with other children and parents. "In the past children would have pen pals but now they can easily have contact with children all over the world."

The stakeholders also pointed out that children could become exposed to stereotypes on the screens affecting their behaviour. They suggest we should be looking into the content that the children are watching, liking and sharing on online platforms such as "TikTok".

The stakeholders specifically mentioned television and its content being very loud, colourful, over the top, fast-moving in an 'unnatural' way and very *distractive*, which could all possibly affect children's mental health.

The stakeholders also said that we could be using *gamification* and screen time to positively affect children's behaviour by encouraging children to go outside and learn about their environment and even to possibly benefit their environment. Pointing out the importance of peer review and again the competitiveness as a strong cultural characteristic in the south-eastern part of Europe. The use of children's *social media* and influencers were brought up to research the children. Furthermore, influencers could also be used to positively affect the mental health of children because of the enormous impact they have on them.

Stakeholders saw screen time affecting the **resilience** of children. This is potentially caused by the

feasibility of fast switching between exposures in the digital world as soon as something is not to their liking, lack of peer review and not having to deal with the emotions and actions of other peers. It was also said there is a rise in **ADHD** diagnoses seen alongside the rise of screen usage which could be correlated. The stakeholders additionally pointed out that there could be a bias concerning ADHD in over diagnosing due to the possibility to receive funds after being diagnosed with ADHD and the likelihood of ADHD being caused by some prenatal exposures.

The stakeholders indicated that the internet can also be used to learn and develop *digital skills* which was said to be of importance in the modern world. However, the stakeholders were also worried that screen time will only make bright children cleverer at the cost of the rest.

The stakeholders saw **government and policies** as an essential part of the exposome research. First, by potentially affecting children's cognitive development and mental health in positive or negative ways through rules and legislations such as the COVID measures and giving access to services. But second to that by affecting what is done with all the knowledge gained through exposome research or any other exposure research. The stakeholders observed that when there are no legislations and mandatory effective policy changes, the governments will not put the obtained knowledge into use even when the evidence is strong and backed up by the World Health Organization. As a result, they keep the approach to curing instead of preventing negative health impacts with the support of public health. It was suggested that guidelines, adjusted to different countries, could help. They also proposed the direct involvement of municipalities because they sometimes still have goodwill to make a change even when it is not mandatory.

The stakeholders also mentioned the **economic status** of the child's social environment and the **access to services** to be of impact on children's mental health and cognitive development. This can be through the availability of appropriate *child care, (mental) health care* and psychosocial support, *disability care, school and education* or the option to receive *mediation or violence protection* but even something small as having the possibility to read a *book*, go outside and have the possibility to be in a place where they can relax, can have an effect.

Governments in Bulgaria were said to have been violating children's rights by *institutionalising* children in 'orphanages' even when they had parents. These institutes were portrayed as free childcare, but they did not provide proper service or care. This rendered Bulgaria with the highest rate of abandoned children in the past and causes mental health and cognitive developmental problems.

In Bulgaria there has also been a problem of *incorrect diagnosing* of children with anti-social behaviour in case of misdemeanours such as stealing, running away from school or home. In this way the child is held responsible instead of looking properly into the circumstances which are causing this behaviour, which often involve lack of family support and poverty. These so-called 'status crime' convictions cause children to be sent away into *correctional institutes* or 'social pedagogic schools' where they often learn criminal behaviour from peers instead of being supported and reformed by the institutes. Through the years changes have been made and the number of institutes has gone down but the philosophy behind the system appears not to have changed and the problem is being diverted into other forms.

The stakeholders mentioned the importance of raising **awareness around mental health** and environmental dangers but on the other hand also emphasized that **overinforming** on environmental dangers can become a potentially harmful exposure on its own by increasing **stress**. The stakeholders pointed out that there still is a big stigma around mental health in South-Eastern Europe and reformation of mental health care is needed. In this mental health environment, there is mainly focus on treating the disease and there is little to no place for prevention. The stakeholders also indicated that we should be looking more into what interventions and methods effectively benefit the children instead of looking at the diagnose they received.

Mental health: The stakeholders described the mental illness outcomes as the **emotional status** of a child or the way a child is emotionally performing. Other internalizing outcomes the

stakeholders referred to were **anxiety** and **trauma** which was said to be a present-day problem often caused by violence and abuse and with no proper support could lead to **depression** or even **suicide**. Aside from the previous mentioned **concentration, agitation, aggression** and **ADHD** outcomes no other externalizing symptoms were brought up by the stakeholders. Furthermore, the stakeholders touched upon the **well-being** of children including *happiness, calmness* and *secureness*, **eating disorders** and the possibility of mental health issues appearing as other **health issues**.

Age categories: Multiple stakeholders emphasized that they would like to see more research on the environmental exposures during the early age, or first 1000 days, and on teenagers and referred to the prenatal age in the previous specified situations.

Annex 2 World café 18 May 2021

Participants: Dimitri (D), Licia (Li), Ana (A), Laura (L).

Three questions were addressed in this session.

- 1) The internal, external and social exposures you consider as potentially harmful to children's mental health and cognitive development.

D: traumatic events in the family environment; the parents are sometimes also victims of the situation. It's hard to protect children in such situations [e.g. when there's no clear abuse by the parents], and these problems start in early life.

Li: works on a research project about kids/teenagers that take care of parents, these caring responsibilities are a risk factor for future mental health problems, but it can also have a positive effect. These children should be supported to mitigate the risks and help them enhance the possible positive effects of their caregiving.

A: in children with chronic diabetes, traumatic events such as a lot of stress is a risk factor. The family environment can influence their mental health in both positive and negative ways. These parents/families and children should be empowered to deal with the situation.

D: caring for family members can also be part of the education and identity of children, it can also help them cope with their mental health problems or traumas. Mental health is increasingly linked to physical diseases via epigenetic mechanisms. He's performing [or has performed?] a meta-analysis on biomarkers in depression; these biological indicators aren't looked into much when signaling mental health problems but can indicate early signs of mental health problems, earlier than psychologists/health professionals can detect signs.

L: many factors are interrelated, for example biomarkers of stress can be linked to SES factors, and there's multiple causes for this relation. There's trend to collect more data, but that can lead to problems distinguishing the trees from the forest, it's good to have a clear focus in research and not just collect huge amounts of data.

D: agrees with this trend for big data; but it's difficult to combine different [treatment?] approaches in one analysis, for example in France it's hard to get funding for studying combined approaches when the components have already been studied separately. To overcome these funding difficulties a network meta-analysis can be an option, this uses pooled information from different approaches. Qualitative analyses are also increasingly performed.

- 2) The internal, external and social exposures that you consider as potentially beneficial to children's mental health and cognitive development.

A: contact with peers and other families that deal with similar issues and situations can have a positive effect on mental health in diabetes children and their families. It's easier to connect to peers than to health professionals and this way promotes empowerment. Her organization in Portugal is organizing summer camps that are remarkably successful: children feel less lonely, and they learn from peers how to deal/cope with their disease. They also organize meetings/courses for families to share experiences and learn from each other.

Li: for child caregivers it can be good to build relations with other significant others, not the sick parents or family members involved in the caregiving, but for example teachers can play a significant role, this can help coping with the situation and prevent mental health issues.

L: controllability is also a key factor; to have some degree of control, feelings of helplessness and lack of control can negatively influence mental health. Children should go outside and experience that their actions do something in the world.

Li: giving children and their family information about the disease and situation can increase their sense of control.

D: in education more psychological and scientific insights/theories should be applied to improve the school environment, children should learn how to use tools and gain skills instead of sitting still all day, this way they can learn how to be in control and to be responsible

L: there's been studies that show that green space can be beneficial for the microbiome; USA research measured people's geolocations, and found that more diverse environments was related to better moods

A: physical activity can have biological (physical), behavioral and mental health benefits. Routine and a schedule are also particularly important in dealing with a [chronic diabetes] disease.

- 3) The mental health problems and cognitive developmental disorders in children that you observe being affected by all exposures and the children affected by these exposures.

Compilation of answers:

- Anxiety, depression, behavioral issues, risk on addiction later in life
- Micro inflammatory status.
- There's a thin line between what is considered to be a disease and what's not – there's a grey area.
- L. mentioned research domain criteria initiative as an alternative to the DSM criteria – it considers biomarkers of psychopathology whereas the DSM is based on psychological questionnaires.
- Both are debatable and have pros and cons.

Annex 3 World café session with Dutch Stakeholders 17 June 2021

There were three participants at the online session. They were from the Netherlands.

Three themes were addressed in this session.

Theme1 - The internal, external and social exposures you consider as potentially harmful to children's mental health and cognitive development.

Theme 2 – The internal, external and social exposures that you consider as potentially beneficial to children's mental health and cognitive development.

Theme 3 – The mental health problems and cognitive developmental disorders in children that you observe being affected by all exposures and the children affected by these exposures.

Participants: Eveliene D. **(ED)**, Karin **(KB)**, Emily M. **(EM)**

Theme1 - The internal, external and social exposures you consider as potentially harmful to children's mental health and cognitive development.

ED – role of parents, production of food (packaging materials), breastfeeding can be a protective factor against obesity, but much has been researched about nutrition. But the breeding ground in which products are produced is also interesting.

Stressors in certain groups – low SES, poverty, reduced skills

Air quality can also play a role.

KB – highly educated parents also have stress.

EM – low SES has often been like this for many generations, across generations is interesting. Aging is a stress factor, apart from SES etc. So don't just keep an eye on low SES groups, every parent can have a backpack that affects the development of the child.

KB – for food, also view packaging material.

EM – lack of exercise affects brain development – and that influences future generations.

Moderator: what is measured in your field in terms of (bio)markers?

ED: too little

KB – we look at the manifestations of that, anxiety disorder, panic etc. [looking at the effect side]

EM – if there are behavioural problems, we look back at what went 'wrong' in early life, but what non-medical factors and signalling instruments are now slowly being done.

RD – the family situation is already being looked at (context)

ED – and it also looks at childcare and the context there.

KB – good development: midwives can already identify whether mother/family are vulnerable (broad definition), then youth nurse can visit the family to see what makes the family vulnerable and help is then offered.

Peter: EQL wants to set up interventions – could we continue to talk about how that could be fitted into prenatal screening in the coming years?

ED – shelter can be needed for a variety of reasons. Different institutions around such a family all look at the context,

EM - but can be improved, it would help to be able to show what the consequences are if not signalled in time.

Theme 2 – The internal, external and social exposures that you consider as potentially beneficial to children’s mental health and cognitive development.

Breastfeeding.

ED – social context family, which needs to be supported enough.

RD – resilience among children and parents; Resilience, which can be done in primary/secondary school. 'Children's rights game' you can talk to children about the situation at home and teach them that, for example, being beaten is not normal.

KB – Prenatal home visits are also an attempt to make people more resilient.

EM – Intervention firm parenting, teaching children to get to know their feelings/emotions/boundaries.

KB – In response to the corona crisis, mental health is a hot topic.

ED – Perception that it always must be 'good', on social media – children are sometimes allowed to be angry, etc.

ED – Placing children from troubled families in a different context can help positively.

EM – The circle can be broken if social network also takes on more, not just the mother/parents.

ED – lots of opportunities to move,

EM - initiatives for play environments are needed.

KB – Prevention agreement (smoking, exercise) and mental health will be added. Physical education has been reduced, but now it is seen how important it actually is.

EM – Child health clinics that are designed to stimulate exercise can make parents aware.

KB – Financing system does not provide the right incentives – the more children you have in treatment, the more money you get, '**normalize**' / medicalize, parents are perfectionists, pressure to perform (HAVO is not enough), society changes in that and not necessarily for the better, performance pressure among children and parents (education, financial), CITO tests.

EM – Be careful with risk factors, especially look at what causes certain factors to cause or don't cause something and pay attention to positive aspects that parents also have in the home.

Theme 3 – The mental health problems and cognitive developmental disorders in children that you observe being affected by all exposures and the children affected by these exposures.

Suicidal thoughts as a result of Corona.

KB – Deterioration in eyes/vision, dentists are also busier than ever – but perhaps not linked to mental health.

ED – Coping strategies, how to deal with things.

EM – Also deal with the pressure you think you will get from outside, role social media e.g.

ED – Students in loneliness is a theme, gaming addiction,

KB – Panic and stress attacks, anxiety disorders

EM – In young children, it is often difficult to see because the child cannot express it on their own and parents do not see it.

Moderator – 'eco anxiety'? ED doesn't see that, but fear of failure does.

Moderator – Autism? KB: It's more common than it used to be, but the spectrum is also wide. EM: it is also seen more, and parents sometimes have difficulty accepting it, it is important that there is room to allow children/adults with a diagnosis to function, remove labels and emphasize the positive sides.

KB – Premature birth may also be a risk factor, which is still being investigated with birth care professionals. Promising start of project will also look at the preconception phase, which is even more relevant now with corona time.

Annex 4 Mentimeter questions and answers stakeholder forum in Ljubljana

Session Governmental or geographical level of needed policy implementation

GOVERNMENTAL OR GEOGRAPHICAL LEVEL OF NEEDED POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

1. Children's mental health problems occur where...?

GOVERNMENTAL OR GEOGRAPHICAL LEVEL OF NEEDED POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

2. The most favorable scale of implementing the research results related to social exposure into policy making would be on:

3. Do you think that each city can provide basic services, clean air and water, enough places where children can play, learn and grow?

4. What scale do you think the research results on children's mental health can be best applied into policies?

Session: Bridging Mental Health and local interventions

BRIDGING MENTAL HEALTH AND LOCAL INTERVENTIONS

1. Do you think we need environmental impact assessment tools to study children's mental health?

BRIDGING MENTAL HEALTH AND LOCAL INTERVENTIONS

2. Do you think we need environmental impact assessment tools to study children's cognitive development?

Session: Bringing all countries in Europe at a higher level of science and policy making

BRINGING ALL COUNTRIES IN EUROPE AT A HIGHER LEVEL OF SCIENCE AND POLICY MAKING

1. Do you think that all countries in Europe have enough knowledge to make policies on children's mental health or cognitive development?

2. Do you think that all countries in Europe have enough budget to make policies on children's mental health or cognitive development?

3. Should the level of results of Equal-Life be made adaptable for each city in Europe?

4. What do you prioritise to be improved at city level?

What kind of stakeholder are you?

Annex 5 Stakeholder forum Ljubljana

Theme 1: Scale on which results should focus

The first discussions were about on what scale (neighbourhood, city, country, etc.) the results of the Equal-Life research should focus, and whether a focus should be placed on deprived neighbourhoods. The overall conclusion was that in each country the decision-making power and finances are on a different scale, and that data are often only relevant if they say something about that scale. An example from Slovenia was that a benchmark had been developed in which regions are compared with each other. However, these regions are not decisive entities and do not manage their own finances, thus the results of this benchmark were not used for anything. It was suggested to determine scales that are translatable to each country (e.g. piece of street segment, urban block, neighbourhood, district, city, region, etc.) and to focus/classify results on these scales.

Some additional observations from participants:

- Multi-level model; interventions on all levels should feed into each other.
- Evaluations of effectiveness are missing; what do interventions achieve?
- Social dimension and cognitive dimension are very important; very different for mental health (vs. physical)
- It is easier for people to reflect on physical rather than mental health.
- Exposome research is complex & multidimensional; interventions on various levels are necessary.
- Example of intervention: <https://young.scot/>

Practical aspects: need of stakeholders that research delivers practical outputs; are the researchers aware of stakeholder needs? How to involve stakeholders in the next (research) steps? Matching Equal-Life work with stakeholders (needs). Even if they are aware of their needs, they may not be able to help. For example, data needed are not available at the level that would allow analysis. For example, data on health/wellbeing are only available for municipalities in Slovenia. Those do not allow studies at neighbourhood level for example. Maybe Environmental Atlas can be promoted as source of at least some information on the environment. This is available at least for some examples for the local level. For example noise maps are available at neighbourhood level but only for areas defined in Directive 2002/49/EC. http://gis.arso.gov.si/atlasokolja/profile.aspx?id=Atlas_Okolja_AXL@Arso

Theme 2: Including the impact of environmental factors on mental health factors in all policy making

This conversation started with the question of whether Environmental Impact Assessments are necessary for effective policy making.

The environment was broadly defined to also include e.g. social media, climate change, fear of war, availability of space to play, etc. It was mentioned that the most relevant aspect here is the 'experience

of the environment', instead of the objective design of the environment. Groups continued to discuss what it takes to include mental health and cognitive development as a factor in all policy fields. Impeding factors that were mentioned include difficulties of working together in an interdisciplinary way, uncertainty/unwillingness to look beyond your own policy field, not speaking the same language, and 'lack of mental health literacy'. It was also mentioned that too few evaluations are carried out on the effectiveness of initiatives, making it difficult to convince policy officers/politicians that their policy area has something to do with mental health. The complexity of the concept of mental health (and interventions related to it) was mentioned as a possible factor to connect policy fields: the topic is so complex and versatile that everyone's input is useful and necessary. Client and citizen participation/citizens' initiatives (speaking from the experience of the citizen in which all sectors come together naturally) were also mentioned as a connecting factor between fields.

Theme 3: Setting up effective youth participation

In the last round, we discussed how a bottom-up approach, with the participation of young people and children in research and policymaking can best be set up. The playful paradigm and the 15-minute city were mentioned as good examples. It was discussed that it is difficult to reach a representative group of young people. Finland works with a youth portal, in which young people are asked questions about policy plans. A link to these questions is shared in several ways via social media, with extra effort being put into engaging groups of young people who are out of the picture – for example via Discord discussion platforms and TikTok. The importance of training children and young people in policy participation (for example at school), giving them the confidence that their input counts, and improving the involvement of less privileged children /young people was also discussed. As a good example, it was mentioned how children in Canada are encouraged from primary school to speak publicly and to be politically engaged.

Finally, a participant from Scotland talked about how legislating the children's right to involvement in policymaking opened doors to developing approaches to be effective in youth participation.

Supplement: Another good example is the Bundesjugendvertretung (Federal Youth Council, BVJ) in Austria which is the “legally anchored representation of the interests of all children and young people in Austria” (<https://bjv.at/english-information/>).

Mental health plans

We collected mental health plans (with a focus on children) to get a grip on some of the issues that stakeholders are facing in their work.

Mental health policy plans mentioned during the forum:

- In Slovenia, North Macedonia, but not specific for children. See for Slovenia e.g. : <https://www.nijz.si/sl/publikacije/mira-za-dusevno-zdravje-nacionalni-program-dusevnega-zdravja>
- Croatia: national plan for children, however not addressing the settings, physical environment. Addressing health and education. Mental health literacy and healthy living programmes with focus and financial resources for green areas.

- Dutch programme 'Kansrijke start'. <https://www.kansrijkestart.nl/>
- Developmental programme and support for teachers etc. needed (in Austria)
- Scandinavia first thousand-day project reports: <https://norden.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1571297/FULLTEXT01.pdf> ;
<https://www.norden.org/en/publication/first-1000-days-nordic-countries-situation-analysis> ;
<https://norden.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2%3A1640984&dswid=-296>

These plans have been used in the workshops and stakeholders for a as examples of inspiration and of identification of problems in the domain of child mental health and cognitive development.

Annex 6 Some examples of used personas

Annex 7 Co-design workshop in Skopje

The workshop was structured according to different themes. Each theme was introduced by one of the Equal-Life partners.

We used descriptions of personas of different kind of stakeholders in the workshop. The purpose of personas is to create reliable and realistic representations of a key audience. These representations should be based on qualitative and some quantitative user research. We wanted to get some insight of what kind of stakeholders are relevant for cooperation with researchers within the Equal-Life project. Not all possible stakeholders were present. The knowledge of which stakeholders were not present is also relevant information. We must consider how to reach out to those missing stakeholders. Some examples of the different personas that have been developed by the participants are added in the annex 6.

After a welcome and a general introduction, we discussed the different personas and stakeholder representation of the participants. This was followed by sessions according to different themes.

4.1 Theme 1: Co-design tools

This session was introduced by PvdH (INCHES). The session addressed questions on how to work towards implementation of results of Equal-Life into health and environmental policies considering children and youth. Which co-design tools are available? What can we learn from different examples? Which tools could benefit your work?

The working method was a world café setup with 4 groups and 4 questions (4 x 15 minutes). This roundtable discussed the following questions:

- Do you have experience and lessons learned regarding co-design or other participatory approaches? Do you use co-design in your work? Do you use co-design in your work, in your organisation?
- Do you collaborate with other professionals, with scientists, with citizens?
- Do you need to shift policies, projects and/or budgets to children's mental health and cognitive development?
- Do you have tips regarding implementing new tools, new (scientific) evidence in your organisation, your work?

The main considerations were grouped according to the topics: 1) co-design process; 2) awareness raising; 3) co-design tools; and 4) cooperation. The participants gave a broad range of suggestions.

Co-designing process: Learning from and listening to stakeholders need investment, from the start, without presumptions. Non-linear process, sometimes you need to go back to previous steps. Listen to people that are not enthusiastic. Have people in the centre of this process, for example as 'idea generators'. Consider rewarding stakeholders. Stress the advantages of co-design, without mentioning the concept of co-designing explicitly. And outputs / results of such processes are not set at the beginning of the (co-design) process.

Awareness raising: we need good stories and good ‘storytellers’ to bring the topic to the public and to politicians. Positive stories, tailored to regions and countries (culture specific). Shift to prevention approach (policies and funding). More long-term and structural projects (programmes) are needed. There is still a stigma in various countries. Citizens (voters) can plead for a shift to prevention with the politicians.

Tools: important to know the target group, tailor-made products. Best practices. Issues are money and staffing. Various examples such as Lifelines, on data collection. Visual and interactive. Specify the (governmental) level that is addressed. Communication, films, storytelling, etc.. Tools for presenting data. Do not waste a lot of time for no reason.

Cooperation: A distinction needs to be made between politicians and administration within governments. Consider who is in charge, which influences the results of the collaboration. The ones in charge define the agenda, the expected outcomes et cetera. Different channels for collaboration, see participation ladder. However, even the one-way communication (lowest step) is difficult. People using TikTok do not want to read scientific information. Twitter, with scientific information, is not used by ‘the people’. Thus consider the social media source for communication. Collect information from different experts / perspectives and combine that in the communication. Make success visible, which might be different for different stakeholders. And identify ‘what are successes for these different stakeholder groups from the beginning.

4.2 Theme 2: Working on application of tools based on Equal- life results

This session the participants discussed questions such as: What tools suit the different stakeholders? How flexible should we be in applying different tools? How about visualization?

- Feedback was given on data and on structure of the toolbox / demonstrator. The latter must be further developed. In spreading / disseminating the tool we need to consider language. Next step is to select the ‘data themes’ and then detail the (level and type of) data (needs).
- Data visualisation: tip was given to look at the example of the Dutch “Kansenkaart.nl” (see <https://kansenkaart.nl/klasouderslaaginkomen#6.47/52.29/5.285>)
- Data in the toolbox will be both from Equal-Life and from other existing sources. The different WPs will deliver algorithms and functions, and probably not data. We do not expect anonymised data. But aggregation of data would be feasible.
- See presentation in annex 11.

4.3 Theme 3: Working towards translation of scientific results

During this session, the participants discussed questions such as: How easy to understand need the results be? Do we have disconnections between scientists and policymakers? What are barriers? We used a presentation and group discussion. The presentation was focused on tipping points of social behaviour and adoption of change in behaviour by people. See presentation in annex 12.

Summary of feedback given.

- Scientist's opinions are needed, in a way, to translate into policy. The message needs to be clear and with a simple conclusion. Scientists have no contact with policy makers (in various countries). Whereas scientists working in e.g., national public health institutes have more regular contact with policy makers and citizens and are better fit for this. Due to their position, as advisors to ministers; these professionals could be the 'storytellers'. 'Nearness' is an important factor.
- Motivation and interests of scientists can differ from the needs of policy makers. Selection is needed of what kind of analyses you make on your data. The main focus in writing is that other scientists can replicate research and not particular that others can implement the results in practice.
- Lessons from the corona pandemic on scientists communicating to the public and policy makers / politicians involving scientists should be learnt. Suggestion: Prepare 1/2 pagers for politicians/policy makers.

We asked what the problems are on the interaction between stakeholders and scientists. What barriers do you see?

Some main answers:

- Difference in language within scientific community and in communication with decision-makers.
- Policy makers are sometimes impatient, while scientist too little sense of urgency.
- Policy makers have a certain goal and look for information supporting that. Coherency within stakeholder groups is lacking might add to this.
- Different sense of urgency. Motivation of scientist can differ from those of politicians.
- Politicians don't like precautionary principles.
- Poor listening, hearing, during all phases. Information during projects and not at the end.
- Additional barriers in communication: changing of politicians; different goals; education level differences; science is sometimes not applicable; too expensive.
- Timing is relevant and might differ between scientists and policy makers.
- Contacts are not always one-to-one, and thus 'interference' from other contacts might occur.
- The message itself can create a barrier as well. The meaning of the data can be unclear.
- Continuous exposure-response information needs to be provided versus yes/no/no information.
- Creative solutions: PR communicators or journalists, use media.
- We need media to transfer key messages from research and put more pressure on policy makers.
- Decision makers need different kind of information (yes or no) than scientists (can) provide. Thresholds are set based upon various arguments (incl. societal) and thus are always broader than the empirical results.
- Results do not always please policy makers. Policy makers are not (always) involved in research studies.
- Collaboration needs to aim to somehow practical wisdom and not to science or solutions.
- Scientific proposals could be used as examples of support to others to apply for research projects. So, less competition but more collaboration.

- There is an additional barrier between scientists and politicians because scientific papers are published in scientific journals which are not visible for politicians/policy makers.
- There is a need for systematic capacity building of scientists on their role in policy making process and learn how to communicate their findings to politicians.
- Research must be proactive to bring main findings in front of messages.

4.4 Theme 4: Interventions ‘bridging the gap’ as a tool to improve health for all

Presented by: MW (UB) with support from SJ (NIJZ)

In this session, we asked participants to draw on their experience with interventions to map out the steps and factors that they think are part of a generic intervention process. As part of this, we asked to describe examples of social inequalities from their work and consider how the intervention process can be designed to better address such inequalities. We then focused on interventions relating to the built environment – such as what stakeholders know from their neighbourhood or city – to think about important aspects of the intervention process when thinking about how to account for social inequalities in environmental exposures.

This workshop session comprised of various discussions and then a collaborative piece of group work. The initial question that the group discussed together asked participants what an ‘intervention’ was to them, as in what this term means. Then, the group was asked to form a continuum with each person choosing a specific intervention. One end of this continuum represented interventions that exclusively address a physical exposure(s) (including the built environment), while the other end of the spectrum represented an intervention that was exclusively about addressing a social exposure(s). The idea behind this was to prompt discussion about how interventions focusing on the built environment, such as the way a city is built, also has implications in terms of social issues and that it is therefore important to consider issues relating to social inequalities, for example, even if the intervention is not primarily a ‘social’ intervention.

We used an iterative process in that participants were encouraged to start the exercise thinking about the intervention process in general terms, before then being asked to extend this thinking to relate to issues of equity and social inequalities specifically. For example, after brainstorming a general flowchart of intervention steps in groups, each group was then asked to think about social inequalities generally and where it would be important to consider such issues during an intervention process. Finally, participants were asked to consider specific pre-prepared questions relating to equity considerations and whether/how they thought they could be used as part of the intervention process. Physical and social domain must be involved. It is important that we learn from the different perspectives and language used, for example, by the different stakeholders in relation to the intervention process, as their experience varies significantly. In the presentation of the case studies these different policy domains must be identified, clarified as well.

Then, most of the session was about considering the following three phases.

Phase 1: Visual representation of steps in an intervention process (e.g. a logic model)

Phase 2: Where are considerations of social inequalities and an equity perspective relevant?

Phase 3: Questions relating to social inequalities and an equity perspective.

The results of the discussion in these phases are summarised below.

Phase 1: Building a general logic model

In relation to context/monitoring:

- working with municipalities, citizens, professionals/experts/researchers, national governments, EU/international governments, engineers and NGO's
- include experts like teachers -> ask them about problems and solutions + bring the topic to their agenda.
- considering existing norms related to the topic.
- use KPI's ('key performance indicators') to evaluate specific problems.
- mention national level problems.
- deciding on a topic (-> evidence – what's changeable, what's integral?)
- consider innovators & Influences on different generations.
- raise awareness on the intervention topic -> communication.

In relation to implementation:

- raise awareness on the intervention topic -> communication.

In relation to planning:

- Identify needs/problem in the very first step.
- define the problem.
- decide on the target (group).
- identification of affected groups.
- Include experts like teachers -> ask them about problems and solutions + bring the topic to their agenda.
- Considering existing norms related to the topic.
- set up individual goals.
- interventions for parents to educate them on the topic.
- decide on the physical spaces and its access.
- decide on the persons who execute the intervention.

In relation to evaluation:

- Identify affected groups to perform the evaluation with them.
- Inter-evaluation between the different planning steps/phases.
- planning as a spiral procedure (planning -> implementation -> evaluation -> re-planning -> re-implementation -> re-evaluation...).
- putting the defined problem in the centre of evaluation, implementation and planning.
- Use so-called KPI's ('key performance indicators') to evaluate specific problems.

Phase 2 and 3:

In relation to an equity lens:

The texts below were transcribed from handwritten notes from the participants.

- Equity perspectives on the planning process.
- Equity perspectives on the target groups -> planning process: Do we cover with interventions. people with lower socio-economic status?
- Are there certain groups that are disadvantaged?
- Who's affected by interventions? (positive or negative).
- Who benefits?
- Do target groups get disadvantages?
- Do people have the ability to participate?
- Education in different social groups?
- Ad hoc communication strategy? (when decides outcome, how to communicate as part of the intervention, how to communicate depends on social factors).
- Moderating factors: poorness -> cultural differences, languages).
- To look at inequity is important: during planning, during monitoring, during evaluation (parents' intervention), assessment of target population, but really every step.
- Setting goals in the availability of the intervention.
- Deciding on how it's implemented, availability for everyone – physical/online.
- Monitoring the availability of the intervention (region and timely).
- Outcome, share, helping.

4.5 Theme 5: Spectrum of prevention

This was an open session to brainstorm on what kind of prevention should be on the policy agenda. Also, the question was posed on what the expected trends are in children's mental health and cognitive development. And: Why can research be beneficial to change policy? What studies and tools should be used?

A summary of bullet points of the suggestions by the participants:

- School settings can have both positive and negative effects. E.g. high demands, dress code (uniforms), school system (primary to secondary to high school selection), social norms, self-management requirements / capabilities.
- Family: education, single parent, poverty, mental status parents, addiction, violence, crowding, number of children (can be a positive effect), divorce, moving house, trauma.
- Preventive programs, such as Dutch program "Nu Niet Zwanger" (not pregnant now).
- Community, housing, services, neighbourhood (playgrounds, green), social networks.
- Steppingstones in each life phase. We need to have universal knowledge, such as how many green areas are needed for children's mental health, what factors are risky? Things to fix and no-go's.
- Social tipping points:

- 25% of the people make a tipping point occur.
- Examples are given for different societal groups: Anti-vaxers; Fridays for future; White flight.
- Education of parents on how to improve relationship with children and adolescents.
- Force will not work. Surroundings are important. Small plans, too big does not work.
- Collaborating social psychologists, psychologists, behaviour analysts – better understanding of human behaviour.
- Culture, religion, weather change, disasters, accidents, new people coming to the neighbourhood, crises.
- Social norms are detrimental, instances of sudden change, significant implications for welfare.
- Development of communication strategy to promote positive behaviour among children and parents. Children – teachers.

Trend watching

For this session we used the method of asking repetitive ‘why questions’. The starting question was: We do not meet our goal to protect children from mental health problems. Why?

What do you see coming?

Children’s mental health is getting worse. Increase of depression, of anxiety. But is there a real increase or an increase of awareness, analysing, data collection? Allowing the conversation to happen will have higher numbers (and not so much increase the outcomes). Medicalisation could be a reason. The global, overall picture versus (differences in) regional pictures.

4.6 Theme 6: What are the next steps?

The participants, both stakeholder and consortium members, were positive about the workshop. They thought it would be especially useful to continue this kind of work. Suggestions were given on strengthening the network of stakeholders. Communication to all stakeholders. Share communication strategy. How is the communication flow to professionals? WHO, EU, ministries of health, regions etc. Have stakeholders talking about their work. Create and share more concrete examples from WPs. Rebuilding the demonstrator. More and better connections to other WPs. There is a need to know what is going on. Participants need a few preliminary results or outputs for involving stakeholders. Involve youth in all WPs, as stakeholders, we are talking about their lives. As well as parents. Stakeholder community building, inform about who is coming to the next meeting. Use LinkedIn. Regular updates on the (whole) project, like a newsletter.

Annex 8 Stakeholder forum Milano

Content of the meeting

Three presentations were provided by Equal-Life researchers to provide an overview of the project.

Iv K, National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM), the Netherlands (online) – Early Environmental Quality and Life-course Mental Health Effects

The forum was opened with a presentation by Irene van Kamp, project coordinator of the Equal-Life project. She provided an overview of the project. She shortly explained the background, approach, methods, and analyses of the project, and what public outputs are aimed for.

KPW, Gothenburg University, Sweden (online) – Linking the exposome to mental health and cognitive development among children and adolescents – Conceptual and path models on potential mediators in Equal-Life

Kerstin introduced three important mediators in the Equal-Life research (stress/restoration, self-regulation/coping, and sleep) and the approach to studying how these mediate the impact of the exposome on mental health and cognitive development outcomes.

EvK, National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM), the Netherlands (online) – Health effect analysis

Elise presented how the Equal-Life work package ‘health data match and health effect analysis’ works to integrate the work of the other work packages in the project by harmonizing the cohorts and school studies, analysing specific research questions, and jointly assessing results.

5.1 Equal-Life handbook and toolbox

The handbook and toolbox session were a parallel activity that ran throughout the forum. It was introduced by a short presentation that explained the intent and current definition of what we call the toolbox and handbook. The definitions are under continuous discussion. Since the first stakeholder meeting in March 2022 (Ljubljana, Slovenia) the responsible partners have been requesting feedback from internal (Equal-Life) and external (stakeholders) partners, which is part of an iterative process. The current understanding of the toolbox and handbook are as follows:

- The toolbox should be a tool, or set of tools, which helps those interested in the Equal-Life project (at various levels) to explore, understand, and reuse the resulting outcomes.
- The handbook should accompany the toolbox as a guide to practical use and help conceptualize what is being presented. It should assist the user to understand the connections between the multiple results displayed.

During the whole two-day forum, participants were invited to place sticky notes on a flipchart with impressions or ideas relevant to the toolbox, these could be related or unrelated to the presented contents during the various sessions. The aim was to collect the opinion of the participants regarding their interest in the topics covered, thinking of them as potential future content within the toolbox and handbook.

The input received was similar to the collected ideas in the previous stakeholder meetings as it focuses on the development of tools that can allow guiding and facilitated access to the project contents such

as deliverables, research questions, and features considered in the analysis. Strong interest was also expressed in explanations and training on analysis methods and software developed during the project, with consequent interest in dedicated training sessions.

5.2 World café discussions on Equal-Life presentations

Presenter: **MK**, University of Kaiserslautern, Cognitive and Developmental Psychology (online)

Title presentation: Effects of environmental exposures on mental health, well-being, and cognition in children at the transition from kindergarten to primary school: Concept of a longitudinal field study

World café questions:

- We study the relationship between greenspace, noise, air pollution, social factors, and the cognitive development of children in the period between preschool and primary school.
- From an intervention perspective what associations to analyse would be of most interest for you

World café discussion:

The presentation was regarded as very good, partly a bit hard to understand (particularly the different outcome measurements and how they are related to each other). But the study presented was regarded as quite illustrative about what Equal-Life is dealing with and is better to understand than the cohort data.

Topics/discussion points mentioned were:

- Identify quality aspects of green space that are important to children's development and how they relate to the preferences of their parents.
- Green spaces in residential areas are most important for small children.
- Study the relation between green spaces & quality of time spent in those spaces.

At that point, the group discussed what defines the beneficial quality of green spaces (or other places) in relation to the mental health of children. It was mentioned that the WP5 definition of "time spent" and "frequency spent" is probably a good indicator for an environment beneficial/attractive for children - better than defining "high quality" in terms of the physical features (vegetation, water ...). "Green space needs maintenance" was mentioned here.

The moderators mentioned that the Preschool study is also interested in social exposure/factors. The group discussion, therefore, shifted towards the role of green space for different (socio-economic) target groups.

Topics mentioned here by group 1 and the following groups were:

- Is there a difference in the effect of green space between different SES groups?
- Idea for an intervention: add green space to schools. Schoolyard itself is an equalizer of SES differences.
- This provides equity of access to green space for pupils.

More general ideas for intervention followed:

- Intervention should provide equity in architecture & urban design.
- Bring nature inside the (artificial) city toward creativity.
- Also, animals bring nature back to the city, not the standard elements more creative.
- Consider the didactic aspects of green environment.
- Designing an intervention that is located in a green space (free school lunch in a park during summer – Helsinki) => provides health-beneficial effects of green space and equity to different socio-economic groups.

Besides green space, some groups' members suggested considering other exposures in the preschool study, namely:

- Include digital exposome.
- Impact of electromagnetic radiation on preschool children.
- Also include noise.

Presenter: **CG**, Centre for Cognitive Science TU Kaiserslautern Germany (online)

Title presentation: Causal path modelling in Equal-Life. What has been and what will be done?

World café question:

How should (complex) empirical and statistical results be communicated to the target audience, and how to present these results, to avoid misconceptions?

World café discussion:

Stakeholders discussed that the answer depends on who the target audience is and that there are diverse levels of information that can be discussed. The stakeholders expressed interest in information on what the results represent and how to link it to interventions and practice. It is important to inform on the context of the results – what questions were asked, what data and methods were used, what data was missing, and how was the conclusion reached. It is also important for the stakeholders to know how they can change the outcomes in the real world. Regarding the form of presenting results, several forms were mentioned: short (written) summaries, interactive sessions with stakeholders, cartoons or animations, and interactive online materials. The results must be introduced properly, communicated in a user-friendly and simple way, and the relevance to the target audience should be clear.

Presenter: **AP**, TU Delft, the Netherlands

Title presentation: New methodological approaches to measuring the physical environment

World café questions:

What metrics/indicators are you using in your daily practice (if at all) to assess a neighbourhood's walkability/accessibility/encouragement of active travel behaviour, etc.? What is lacking?

Do you use any available tools/design guidelines from global organizations such as WHO, UN Habitat, etc.? Which ones? What is lacking?

When it comes to improving children's mental health and well-being, which environmental aspects do you consider the most important and why? On what evidence do you prioritize them?

Do you see any potential in the work we presented for your daily practice? What would you need to make this happen?

World café discussion:

All participants agreed that the presentation was very good. Already knowing about this kind of research is an “eye-opener”. Members of this group discussion were impressed with all data gathered and were interested in how they can reach data at a similar level for their cases. They would be interested in reading reports and publications to read more about it on the Equal-Life website. Regarding the topic “green areas” they suggested to add also locations of schools/kindergartens, and playgrounds. Apart from the fact that green areas are discussed it is also important what such areas offer, what are activities supported in such places (recreation, use of digital apps ...). It was suggested that a list of aspects that spatial planners should consider before deciding on new interventions. Planners need active engagement of several stakeholders including residents and feedback from users. It is important to monitor and evaluate the use of the green area and make improvements with time. It is important to know what kind of green areas we need in the city (safety, activities ...). Accessibility is important, need to avoid barriers or cross them (railways ...). It should be a dynamic process. Tools for municipalities are needed to consider the list of aspects that they should consider.

Presenter: **JA & LG**, University of Bremen, Germany

Title presentation: Social Exposome - Concept, application fields, and implications

World café questions:

- Does our research inspire any practical implications in your work?
- Do you see any options to integrate our research in your work?
- Do you see any gaps, which should be addressed in our research?

World café discussion:

Do you see any gaps, which should be addressed in our research?

- One important aspect within Social Exposome should be digitalization and social media: Social reality is highly digitalized, and the increasing global digitalization should be considered when we refer to the social environment, because of the high interrelatedness between the real and the virtual/digital worlds.
 - Social reality is typically perceived through ‘digital filters’ (i.e. use of smartphones, iPads, social media, etc.)
 - The omnipresence of digital devices distracts from the real world and influences our relationships: distraction, loss of focus (e.g. parents and little children → parental investment)
 - Interaction effects between the use of digital advice and socioeconomic/educational background → digital literacy is needed.
- When talking about the Social Exposome we also need to consider community and social interactions at the neighbourhood/district level.
 - Quality of neighbourhoods differs a lot within cities and depends highly on movement or employment patterns.
 - What can be observed is that segregation is wanted by the privileged residents/communities:

- Important → How to break through this aversion and increase tolerance/ openness to achieve regeneration without losing benefits?
 - Young families typically are a constant in neighbourhoods → maybe increase exchange platforms for children to reach acceptance between diverse populations → insight & exchange of living patterns.
 - Look for options to increase community involvement (participatory approach)
- When talking about social interactions we need to define the meaning of social interactions: quality and quantity of interactions.
 - In practice interactions outside specific settings (e.g. school) define the atmosphere for meaning, because here interactions lose their function as “social roles” (e.g. teacher, pupil) but can grow into ‘true’ relationships. Thus, to ‘improve’ interactions, we need to create exchange options outside settings. This understanding may also help to improve neighbourhoods/relations within neighbourhoods.
- For mental health social interactions are of high relevance, as we need to consider both, perception of interactions and behaviour within interactions.
 - To improve communities/neighbourhoods we need money and, thus, we need to convince policy and decision-makers, we need to be outcome-related. But awareness is also highly important which also can be outcome related.

Do you see any options to integrate our research into your work?

- Quality of data: Concrete operationalization options need to be defined to collect good & clean data to draw valid conclusions.
- Reduction of complexity to make it feasible in the field – concrete guidelines would help.
 - E.g. Logic Model for Equity Assessment: name concrete evaluation criteria that are to be followed in the development of interventions.

Presenter: **MD**, TU Eindhoven, the Netherlands

Title presentation: Defining relevant settings by time-activity-sound exposure mapping.

World café questions:

- Could you see this type of study being done in your municipality or another scale you are dealing with in your daily work (neighbourhood/city/province/country)?
- Do you see any benefit to apply our research in your daily work?
- Knowing the types of data we collected, what research questions come to mind? (In other words, can you give any additions/suggestions to our work?)

World café discussions:

Stakeholders found the idea of using behavioural patterns for data collection an interesting approach. The opinions were divided on whether they see this study being repeated in their own field of work, due to costs or privacy. The information that the stakeholders thought of to be beneficial for their work were: SES – noise, quality of life – noise, mental health – noise, and the social differences. It was suggested by the stakeholders to explore the relationship between duration and noise, with the question being: are locations with a higher noise exposure visited for a shorter time? Other suggestions were to connect more data to the existing dataset to investigate the mediation of other exposures

such as green space and air quality and to incorporate subjective sound experience in the future. Finally, the stakeholders would like to see suggestions for interventions, guidelines for when a setting is “good” or “bad” and how to inform parents and teachers better about the effects of noise.

Presenter: **DK**, Jožef Stefan Institute, Department of Environmental Sciences, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Title presentation: Children's (mental) health and participatory research: diversity of levels of inclusion

World café questions:

- How to translate findings resulting from various participatory/CS activities in interventions?
- Which tools (and their features) are to be used for effective engagement of children - also to foster motivation and consequently sustainability of activities?
- Is there room for integration of approached presented into school curriculum?
- How to assess impact of activities/intervention considering specifics of participants (children) involved?
- How to foster the up scaling of the results and their uptake by policy and decision makers?

World café discussion:

In the beginning of the discussion, someone asked for an explanation on what is intervention. The meaning of the word is not sufficiently clear. Discussion went in direction that results from the research are very often not implemented in policies. Decision makers listen at the results coming from research, but they do not consider these results in decision making. We agree that environmental sensors for air pollution and noise exposure can give very valuable data and they should be shared with local authorities. People are sceptical of implementing solutions on children's science.

On the topic- Which tools (and their features) are to be used for effective engagement of children - also to foster motivation and consequently sustainability of activities, the participants gave very interesting proposals. These tools could be games, tools as amusement for children, tools that make children responsible to use, but still, they are not obligatory for children. It is also important to involve teachers and children, teachers could make rating for their development especially in development of emotional skills. Some of these tools could be included in education process and become part of education curriculum, especially for environmental pollution and human health.

We should think to include children in the process of development of tools—co-creation and co-design with children.

Someone gave idea for development of application for daily diary, so we can get picture for time activity patterns.

- How to foster the up scaling of the results and their uptake by policy and decision makers?

For this question, all participants were very sceptical that results will be implemented in the policies.

Presenter: **KB**, senior advisor child & adolescent public health, the Netherlands

Title presentation: Mental Health in the Dutch Public Health sector

World café questions:

- Are you missing items in the wish list?
 - Well-being as a basic condition at school
 - More target group-oriented interventions
 - More accessible interventions; more preventive interventions

- Attention to social and physical factors in relation to mental health
- Data about: - young adults; - migrants; - low socio-economic status
- More qualitative data in the field of mental health.
- Are there already qualitative data about mental health that you would suggest?
- Which qualitative data are most relevant?
- Are there already national research agenda's Mental Health on children's mental health?
- Can Equal-Life be of any support?

World café discussion:

Considering the time, no discussion was held on Karin's presentation.

Presenter: **ES**, City of Helsinki, Finland

Title presentation: Implementing evidence-based psychosocial interventions: an example from Helsinki, Finland

World café questions:

- What kind of national guidance is offered in your field of work?
- How would you apply your experiences in our work?

World café discussion:

First, time was taken to answer questions about the IPC-A intervention. For example, questions about the Finnish health care system in which basic health care to children is provided through the school system, and that the IPC-A is an individual intervention that can be provided by anyone who has completed the training. An important question for Emma is how to get managers in the school and healthcare system to adopt the IPC-A intervention. The intervention is already in the national guidelines; however, this national guidance is not enforced. Barriers in Finland are that managers do not feel that implementing healthcare interventions is part of their job description, as the law is more focused on prevention than interventions.

A few experiences from other countries with this issue were shared: one participant proposed to inform parents about the importance of this intervention so that they will ask schools to implement it. A German participant proposed to start screening for mental health problems to show the magnitude of the problem and create more support for implementing IPC-A or other interventions. Another German participant suggested that it might help to convince insurers that the intervention is cost-efficient, they might then lobby for the intervention in schools and healthcare settings. A participant from Italy proposed that it might help to inform university students about the importance of this intervention and the importance to work interdisciplinary, so that they might change the educational and healthcare systems of the future and will see the value of these interventions when they enter professional life. In Slovenia they encounter similar difficulties in implementing interventions, their barriers are mainly a lack of resources, people, and motivation, and who has the responsibility for the implementation of interventions is not clear.

Presenter: **MW**, NCJ, the Netherlands

Title presentation: Your brain in control?! Universal prevention towards mental health in adolescents

World café questions:

Is there a way in which Equal-Life can help measuring the changes we aim for with this intervention at school?

- we expect to see more interaction between students, outside classes and lunchbreaks.
- we expect to see more interaction between students and teachers, outside scheduled classes, without self-reported research.

In the sequel of the first question: Where can Equal-life help to get insights of change of behaviour by looking from another angle to the situation? In most research on groups and student there are lots of ethical discussions. There's a non-ethical part in Equal-Life that can be helpful.

World café discussion:

The 'Your brain in control' program is looking for (new) ways to evaluate the effects of the intervention. As with other universal prevention programs providing evidence on a single, specific intervention is challenging. A method could be to use social media and – in this case – YouTube videos and posted comments to track, analyse and classify 'the sentiments' (suggestion of / support by QUANTIA). Another question from the program is whether this intervention helps in improving and enhancing the social environment of schools. Will schools be a 'better setting', as researched by Equal-Life, due to this intervention? Can Equal-Life provide indications or causal relations on social environments, school settings, and children's mental health that would support this?

Presenter: **LG**, Cork City, Ireland

Title presentation: Let's play Cork

World café questions:

- Barriers to a more playful city include dedicated full-time resourcing, annual multi-stakeholder budgeting and public liability/insurance costs. Benefits of applying any result from Equal-Life in your daily work: research findings that properly clarify the importance of early preventative interventions. Applied research projects that test these findings would be a great benefit.
- In my presentation I will focus on 2 Cork examples - Let's Play Cork (Playful Paradigm) and Let's Grow Together (Infant and Childhood Partnership). It's important to note: Buy in for a more playful city is always easy – but there is a need for more applied research and committed pilot projects to grow confidence in the ability to deliver larger/more permanent playful city projects.

World café discussion:

- The main challenges are maintenance of the playgrounds and long-term funding. Collaboration between different sectors and departments, and people with different expertise are necessary for further development. That is a good reason for each city to have a healthy city coordinator who will coordinate all of them. Someone mentioned that children need digital equipment for playing in the playgrounds, this could be a very innovative idea.
- Especially important is to consider equity principles to avoid enlarging the gap among different population groups. Lorcan thinks they considered social inequalities when they planned playgrounds.
- A festival of integrated involvement of children, parents, and other adults is an interesting event and important for emotional connection. This event was organized in Estonia, they are not so frequently organized, but they can be a good example of interpersonal connection.

- Evaluation of this intervention in Cork city was not performed, but Lorcan thinks that people are mostly satisfied. There was a proposal for evaluation of the intervention with walking interviews, like walking through the city and asking people what they think and what will they change or add something else.
- Someone mentioned as a good example “playful benches in New Zealand”; benches in the green areas, with different possibilities for playing and stimulation of children’s development.

Presenter: **ISE**, Urban Planning Institute of the Republic of Slovenia

Title presentation: Green spaces for healthier children and youth: recommendations from “Going Out for Health” programme in Slovenia

World café questions:

- What “additional” argumentation to support green space planning and design in practice can you give?
- How can the quality of outdoor living environment affect and improve the mental (and physical) health of children and youth.
- What kind of indicators can be used to measure that?

World café discussion:

- Questions that came up in the discussion were what the definitions are of ‘nature’ and ‘green space’, and that definitions probably differ in different settings. We should involve citizens in defining green spaces and what qualities they appreciate in them.
- Stakeholders also want more insights into how people react to different types of green spaces: what do people like and how is it beneficial to them?
- It is important to have green spaces close to homes and schools and on the routes children take to school, there is not enough data on this yet.
- Introduce digital tools for play in green spaces.

Presenter: **UB**, Social Protection Institute of the Republic of Slovenia

Title presentation: Is it all about location? Spatial Inequalities in the city of Ljubljana

World café questions

- What is the policy relevance and applicability of highlighted data?
- Are policy makers and political decision-makers interested in the results?

World café discussion:

- One question was if there are more inequalities between the areas, e.g.: Are there more facilities in general in the affluent areas? Is this quantifiable for future analysis?
- It was suggested to link the noise exposure data (e.g., from publicly available noise maps) to the data on kindergarten subsidies and see if there are differences in noise exposure depending on the prosperity status.
- We agreed that it is an innovative approach to estimate the prosperity of a neighbourhood and it could be considered to use in Equal-Life as well.

Keynote presentation **SD** (online)

The first 1000 days in the Nordic Countries

The first months and years of children's lives are paramount for their future well-being. Brain development is at its peak and foundations are laid for neural pathways and brain regions that dictate future learning, language, emotion regulation, and behaviour. This lays the foundation for good mental health throughout the lifespan.

The first 1000 days in the Nordic Countries is a three-year Nordic co-operation project launched in 2019. It has been working on an extensive situation analysis of the Nordic countries, reviewing the evidence-base for interventions and assessment tools, and development of policy recommendations. This resulted in three extensive reports on these three pillars.

For more information see: www.first1000days.is/about-the-project

5.3 Using a logic model as a tool to encourage thinking about social inequalities in urban planning interventions

For this workshop session ran by Jenny Ahrens (UB), the goal was to evaluate the applicability of the Logic Model for Equity Assessment using an exemplary intervention on bicycle infrastructure based on the workshop participants' expertise. To do this, five groups were formed, and each group focussed on the three main parts of an intervention: Planning – Implementation – Evaluation.

During the discussion, the following three questions were our guiding questions:

- What tools similar to the logic model are you currently using at work (e.g., guiding questions, frameworks, other models)?
- Can you see the logic model being used in your work?
- What could be added or changed to make the logic model a more useful tool?

As for the different three phases, it was noted that an impact assessment would be valuable within the planning phase and that evaluation needs to be implemented within all phases.

The main takeaway from the discussion with stakeholders and members of Equal-Life was that it needs to be made noticeably clear that this Logic Model for Equity Assessment is not another process-model but is about assessing the equity aspects in the three main phases of an intervention. Ideas to improve this was to emphasize this even in the visual model by using "trigger words".

5.4 Evaluating children's access to public outdoor play space

In the session on Evaluating Children's Access to Public Outdoor Play Space, RT and AP (TU Delft) collected knowledge from the Equal-Life stakeholders in an interactive workshop session. TU Delft aims to measure children's access to play spaces in cities, to be used for the enrichment of the Equal-Life cohort and school study data sets. The goal of this session was threefold: to collaboratively identify the factors that limit or promote children's access to play space; to connect these factors to elements in

the urban environment; and to assess the latest work-in-progress approach of TU Delft in measuring children's access to play space.

First, RT introduced the topic to the stakeholders and provided them with a brief overview of the theory that the workshop was built upon. Then, stakeholders were asked to contribute with suggestions of factors that limit or that promote children's access to play space as keywords, followed by a brief plenary discussion of the most prevalent limiting (i.e., lack of safety or security, traffic, and lack of places suiting age or multiple generations of users) and promoting factors (i.e., safety, other children, informal places to play, and equipment for children with reduced abilities).

Second, both stakeholders and Equal-Life participants split into 6 groups, each at their own table, to discuss children's accessibility in a specific urban case: 3 tables focused on Ljubljana, Slovenia, and 3 tables on Milan, Italy. Participants familiar with either Milan or Ljubljana were presented with the corresponding city, while others were spread over tables to ensure variety in expertise and geographical background. At each table, an Equal-Life moderator guided the process. Participants discussed photos and maps of the city at hand and pinpointed what could limit or promote children to access play spaces.

Third, participants were presented with a map overlay on top of the map of the second round, made by TU Delft to model children's access to play space. Specifically, these overlays showed places they identified that may attract children's play (i.e., playgrounds and small parks), or that may be a barrier to children who want to access a space to play in the city (i.e., transport and natural infrastructures). Participants discussed to what extent they agreed with the barriers and places presented on the maps, as well as what should be omitted or added to better reflect practice.

Throughout the second and third rounds, participants contributed their knowledge by means of annotations, drawings, and sticky notes. Participants also elaborated on experiences from their own life or town, which were captured in audio recordings. TU Delft will use these to understand the potential and limitations of using such data to model children's access to play space in the Equal-Life project.

Preliminary take-away messages from the participants to RT and AP include: The size and shape of parks, time of day, movement trajectories, and surrounding land use and activities matter when assessing children's access to play space; Good quality infrastructure is important; And knowledge from local experts or children is crucial to get a complete understanding of children's access to public outdoor play space in the urban environment at hand.

5.5 Policy recommendation perspectives

PvdH introduced the session with a short presentation on the ecological doughnut model and the DPSIR model. The doughnut model by Kate Raworth (2012) is a visual framework for sustainable development, combining the concept of planetary boundaries with the complementary concept of social boundaries. The DPSIR model (drivers, pressures, state, impact, and response model of intervention) is a causal framework for describing the interactions between society and the environment.

These models were developed in the context of planetary health and the environmental sciences, to describe and clarify complex systems. The participants were invited to think of applying an adapted version of the DPSIR model to the context of children’s mental health and cognitive development. The results from the discussions on drivers, pressures, status, mediators, and outcomes are on the next page.

5.6 Spectrum of interventions, screening methods, toolbox and handbook in practice

PvdH introduced the session with a short presentation and two mentimeter questions.

Participants were divided into five small groups and received descriptions of several promising interventions for children’s mental health. The groups discussed the interventions on usefulness (for Equal-Life and in general), barriers in the application, connection to own work, and if and how the Equal-Life project can add to the intervention. At the end of the discussion, each group shortly presented one intervention they considered most fitting to the Equal-Life context.

5.7 What are the next steps?

In this final session, the stakeholders and Equal-Life researchers split into two separate groups. The stakeholders reflected on the tips and tops of the stakeholder forum from their perspective. The Equal-Life researchers discussed next steps to take in the stakeholder activities.

Stakeholder reflections

Tops:

- The highest evaluated part of the forum program was the workshop ‘Evaluating children’s access to public outdoor play space’: engaging, easy, accessible.
- Stakeholders highly valued the possibilities for informal discussions, they would have liked even more moments for this.
- The combination of giving and receiving was appreciated.
- Stakeholders appreciated learning more about the Equal-Life project.
- The location and catering were highly valued.

Tips:

- Stakeholders would have liked more breaks as the program was quite demanding and they liked informal interactions.
- The number of presentations on different topics was too high for one moment for discussion afterwards (world café discussions)
- The technical equipment should have been tested before starting the sessions, or technical support needs to be available.
- Define the level of interventions (from international to neighbourhood level).

- Stakeholders felt they did not know well enough what was expected from them before and during the forum, especially as stakeholders come from different fields and organizations.

Suggestions for future stakeholder activities:

- It would be nice to be in a park when discussing parks and green spaces; add outdoor activities or site visits to the program.
- Having one overarching topic to focus on might make it easier to concentrate, rather than having many different topics from different disciplines.
- Use the stakeholders to test the project findings.
- Organize additional activities between the in-person meetings to maintain and increase the cohesion of the network that was created in the forum, via digital means (e.g., Zoom or Teams)

Next steps discussed by Equal-Life researchers

With regards to future stakeholder communication and activities, the Equal-Life researchers discussed:

- Frequent (digital) information and updates
- Organizing continuing interactive (in-person) sessions for stakeholders and researchers.
- To explore pilots or test projects of Equal-Life findings at stakeholder organisations.
- To send save the date(s) for the next stakeholder activities.
- In the first quarter of 2023, an agenda for stakeholder activities will be distributed.

Annex 9 Co-design workshop Como

The workshop was a live workshop. A total of 15 persons attended (live 12, 3 online). The workshop took place at the Politenico in Como.

Sessions were conducted on how to read frameworks and different conceptual models on exposures, mediators, settings and life course stages. Another session discussed the use of tools and how these should be designed. Another session dealt with the reflection on the prioritization of research questions of Equal-Life and their link to daily practice of the stakeholders. A session on social exposome looked at the integration of social and physical domain. This was considered as very important by the stakeholders. Two final sessions were conducted on 1) Data and harmonization; and 2) Conceptual modelling with semantic technologies.

Introduction presentation on conceptual models

Presentation WP1 (DS, Partner ZEUS): formulate theories and mechanisms -> framework and different conceptual models (exposures, mediators, settings, life course stages).

Some mentioned highlights:

Social practices affect the impact, as well as social and physical environments. Translated into research questions, which are “tested’ in in-depth studies (sleep study and preschool study) and in cohort studies, including enrichment of the data. Results will be available end of 2023 / beginning of 2024 (externally).

An identification of **key exposures** within the human exposome; this could for example be exposures like access to play areas, noise levels during sleep, and quality of interaction between child and parent, depending upon the health outcomes.

Discussion on the concept of **mediator**, such as sleep and stress. How do stakeholders use that?

Suggested by stakeholder: It is an ‘outcome’ that is an entrance point for unpicking/understanding what’s behind this. An inventory on stress among parents now includes a question on whether one *minds* experiencing stress. Poverty is an essential factor, the main factor, as well. Poverty is part of the social exposome. Housing in combination with poverty.

Poverty is not used as a term in Equal-Life but can be found in the ‘inequalities’ perspective of the research.

Adding another mediator, such as access to (social / health) services could be considered?

Session on tools

Make a distinction between types of stakeholders. Who are you addressing? Information for decision making. (Inter)national level, city level, community level and settings level. Make the tool according to *simplicity* principles (i-Pad).

We discussed the definition of tools and collected feedback on the type of tools considered.

During the session we returned to the concept of the tool. The list of project outcomes was shown, and we were asked to reason about the target concept.

Link at the presentation used to support the session:

<https://view.genial.ly/649cb440c29def001e132beb>

Notes from whiteboard/sticky notes on what can be linked to concept of tools: best practices, action perspective, interventions, training/education, application, software, questionnaire, skill, instrument, advice, device, series of webinars, guide, policy brief, 'the self', collection of data, collection of guidelines, e-learning, infographics. Interaction, intervention, practices, (self)assessment, policy making, measuring exposure data, build something, 'the other'.

Session on research questions moderated by INCHES

Tables with the research questions considered in the project were presented in the discussion. The questions had been sent in advance to stakeholders to have time to read and understand them.

See annex 14 for tables with research questions. Initials are used for names of stakeholders.

On table 1.

G: as a professional you see a child as a whole and therefore it is hard to distinct and prioritize singular factors. Awareness of optimal brain development is there; how exposures contribute or form a risk would be relevant knowledge.

M: focussing on (his task to) increasing children's mental health made prioritising easier (language, motor skills and well-being (nrs 2, 4 and 5). And be aware of the differences in Europe, different school systems, institutionalised inequalities.

On table 2.

G: sub questions under nr. 12. What is impact of chaotic environments and of supportive social environments, and what can we do to make a change?

E: sub questions under nr. 16 on internalizing behaviours. Related to the increase of eating disorders.

M: similar to G. Note: once you look for a problem, you will find a problem (example of mental health of Dutch girls).

For the toolbox: provide instructions on how to use the data, on what is known and on what is not yet known.

Access to services, use of and quality of is (maybe) lacking in the data. Part of cohort data and/or enriched data? If so, probably part of the social exposure.

On table 3.

Agreement was reached on the importance of questions on: How does a child's perspective of exposures differ from an adult's perspective? (nr 24) and are there subgroups of children that follow different exposome paths over life? (Nr 21.).

Built environmental factors is a crucial question as well to inform spatial planners.

Session on Translation of scientific results into tools moderated by Quantia

The insights from the co-creation workshop in Como provided a valuable understanding of how stakeholders utilize tools in their professional environments and offered feedback on the demonstrator's advantages and disadvantages.

Main interest was seen in all outputs from WP4 and low interest in WP5 for stakeholders, except for the maps (and higher for researchers).

Related to the development of a toolbox several suggestions were provided. Stakeholders mentioned preferred formats: guidelines, visuals, 'easy' website, policy brief, communication material, interactive webpages.

Action: raise importance of discussing preliminary results with stakeholders during upcoming catch-up session. Researchers need to learn to communicate with / to non-academics. Make the language work for the end-user.

Lunch time with external activity: Tour of the urban area outside the Politecnico. Walking discussion on the accessibility and quality of a local playground.

Session on social exposome moderated by UB, INCHEs and NIJZ

Session started with an explanation about the social exposome.

Social exposome: a novel conceptual framework. Goal a realistic portrayal of the complex social environment. Characteristics of the framework: Multidimensionality, reciprocity and timing and continuity. See paper at:

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0013935123012896?via%3Dihub>

Three pathways are identified in the model developed by UB: empowerment, resilience and susceptibility or vulnerability, and embodiment as additional feature.

Integration of social and physical exposomes. Question by stakeholder: Why integration? Answer: To understand mechanisms / pathways that drive the patterning / combinations of exposures and how they together and holistically affect health.

Starting point is to develop reliable and valid metrics to measure the complex external environment, comprised from social and physical indicators.

Integration of social and physical domains leads to another starting point towards a holistic external exposome concept.

Discussion notes:

Generally, the questions in Equal-Life are considered to be complicated questions. They are space dependent, contextual, cultural. In some cities noise is an issue, whereas in other cities it is air pollution. The expressed needs of citizens might not be the (health) issue or have the biggest impact on health.

More affluent neighbourhoods in Cork, have better green, playgrounds and lower exposures. In contrary to less affluent neighbourhoods where neglected, unsafe areas even are closed.

Social and infrastructural access of space for teenagers, girls is an item of concern.

Interesting tools: WHO HEAT tool on combined exposures and the Place Standard Tool.

Further suggestion: create participation of children in decision making: youth councils, youth representatives. But quite different to involve, various experiences.

A complex / combined model is interesting, but a specific action – coming out of the model – is key.

The social and physical environments are the contexts within which stress (of children and parents) occurs. This raises the question where to start at an individual level? Where to start at group, municipal, regional etc. levels?

Maslov's hierarchy of needs: if the basis is unstable and the physical environment is continuously interfering, it is hard to intervene and address the mental health problems.

What is the impact of addressing problems, making (vulnerable) people aware of their health problems? Or something else?

Related to reducing inequalities: addressing the entire population versus specific groups? Example from Utrecht tool on 'equal opportunities'.

Multi level governance: how to strengthen interaction between various levels of government. What gaps need to be addressed?

Putting these topics / patterns on the (policy) agenda. Equal-Life will not be able to provide tailor-made solutions (managing the expectations).

The conceptual framework will be refined using the analysis outcomes of the different work packages in the project and of the stakeholder's input.

Through social interactions individuals are impacted by social and physical exposures.

Requests:

- for access to definitions of all the terms used in the social framework and in general. This suggestion is made in order to have a common language and understanding, for stakeholders as well as Equal-Life consortium members.
- Can children be involved be as well in meetings?

Interaction session: Social-environmental dimensions circle (taped on the floor).

Ljubljana: including social aspects and health impact assessments in spatial planning.

Integrating Equal-Life results into health impact assessments regarding mental health and cognitive development outcomes.

Session on Data and harmonization presented by Jenny Selander (KI)

A presentation was given on mapping of existing content in the cohorts and harmonization (protocol) and code book.

There are Analysis teams on: diagnosis team (mental health), internalizing / externalizing (mental health), cognition, well-being, and on biomarkers. Selection of life phase where outcomes are (most) relevant.

Analysis plan:

- Which residential (maternal) physical and social exposures during pregnancy are associated with ADHD diagnosis?
- Which residential physical and social exposures at age 0-3 years are associated with an ADHD diagnosis?
- What is the association between prenatal physical and social exposome and an ADHD diagnosis? To what extent is this association mediated by preterm birth / SGA/LBW?
- What is the association between physical and social exposome at age 0-3 years and an ADHD diagnosis? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep (measured at age 0-3 year)?
- Which residential (maternal) physical and social exposures during pregnancy are associated with autism diagnosis?
- Which residential physical and social exposures at age 0-3 years old are associated with an autism diagnosis?
- What is the association between prenatal physical and social exposome and an autism diagnosis?
- What is the association between physical and social exposome at age 0-3 years and an autism diagnosis? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/ sleep (measured at age 0-3 years)?

Stakeholders' role particularly relevant and valuable in interpreting the analysis outcomes. Move away from statistics into interpretation (RIVM- Irene van Kamp).

Adding data: in EHEN context – or its follow-up (proposal for new EU project: I-EHEN).

Interactive session on Prioritising data (categories)

We wanted to know which categories of data are important in the view of stakeholders. Different categories of data were mentioned. Prioritised categories are mental health, fluid intelligence, socio-demographic factors, psychosocial stress, relationships and social support, educational mobility, health characteristics, learning and teaching conditions, living conditions.

Although all have (some) importance.

Reflections on this 'exercise':

- We should have done this at the start of the research project.
- Combining research and practitioners' arguments – interdisciplinary approach
- Combine these priorities with the research questions priorities.

Session on Conceptual modelling with semantic technologies (Quantia, MB)

Within Equal-Life a semantic knowledge search tool will be developed: a tool to help you finding a specific document. What is an ontology? A model of (some aspect of) the world. Introduces vocabulary relevant to the domain. Specifies meaning (semantics) of terms. Formalised using suitable logic. Shared among multiple organisations.

Creating classes. Creating subclasses. Creating a class instance. For example: artist is a class. Painter and sculptor are subclasses of the artist class. And Leonardo is a painter (hence, also an artist). Leonardo is not a class. And then creating additional class instances: for example, Da Vinci, age, birth date. Creating class instances through class properties, for example: Leonardo paints the Monalisa (painting), Michelangelo paints the Sistine Chapel (painting), Michelangelo sculpts the David (sculpture) . And then an AI tool can know that Leonardo creates the Monalisa or that Michelangelo creates the Sistine Chapel and the David.

Stakeholder help needed to improve /reflect on the tool.

Feedback stakeholders: search the evidence and best practice, take theory and implement that. Not interested in what is at the back of that (website, tool etc). Technique versus content.

Search engine optimisation. Conceptual model of Equal-Life is the ontology for the tool prototype. To be validated by stakeholders (e.g. in stakeholder forum in Helsinki). Have a practitioner and IT expert working side by side.

Organising the input for the machine learning is a major step. IvK: note, there are more conceptual models in Equal-Life, thus need to use the definition documents / go a layer deeper. Suggestion: prepare an example to further discuss / pre-test with stakeholders. Starting point for the ontology could be the conceptual model of WP1.

Final conclusion:

A Demonstrator version of the toolbox/handbook was prepared and reviewed with stakeholders at the WP8 co-creation meeting in Como. Additionally, an Editorial Board was formed to organize and incorporate results and findings from the Equal-Life project into the toolbox and handbook. This board, adopting a top-down approach, comprises members with diverse expertise in areas such as tools and training, knowledge management, handbook and toolbox development, stakeholder expertise, and communication and coordination. Their goal is to make the project's outcomes easily understandable and relevant to the public.

Annex 10 Stakeholder forum in Helsinki

Thursday 7th September

The meeting started with a concise explanation of Equal-Life research, the conceptual framework and the program of the 2-day workshops organized by WP8 (stakeholder involvement) and WP9 (toolbox and training).

The conceptual framework: the totality of internal, social and physical exposures, over a lifetime, to better understand the causes of and processes related to mental health and cognitive functioning, with potential mediating pathways, providing a possibility for interventions along the life course.

Expected results: early life exposure to urban planning related factors (noise, air), social factors (parental stress, social economic), biomarkers related to environmental and social exposures.

Presentation: Overview of preliminary results /updates (DS, Zeus)

Aim of WP1 (on mechanisms) is to formulate theories and mechanisms, for how exposome links to mental health and cognitive development of children and adolescents and to understand how stress / restoration, self-regulation / coping and sleep may affect these relationships.

Research questions are studied in-depth in sleep and pre-school studies and in the cohort studies (data), enriched with new data. Examples of data available in the cohorts and/or are illustrated.

Reflections from stakeholders: coping, digital environment and daylight are (yet) missing in research. Outcomes influence the exposome; that arrow / link is 'missing' in the conceptual framework. This can be modelled though (in WP7).

Presentation: Measuring access to public spaces (TUD)

This workshop consisted of two parts.

Part 1: In the first part, we examine which factors influence pedestrian access to public spaces and for whom. Using an interactive card game, we will prioritize varied factors that affect pedestrian accessibility and discuss how we can practically measure them.

Part 2: In this second part we focus on how to assess children's access to greenspace in the city as a place to play, socialize, be active, and so on, ultimately contributing to healthy urban environments. Using interactive tools, we will collaborate to create ideal metrics for children's access to greenspace and discuss several metrics that have been implemented by TUD so far.

Related to part 1: SDGs, target 7: by 2030 provide universal access to safe, inclusive and accessible, green and public spaces in particular for women and children, older persons and persons with disabilities. How to identify, assess, establish / maintain these areas? Group work on what factors and for whom? And on measuring greenspace.

Identifying and prioritizing urban factors: overlap in factors, importance of proximity, shadow, safety, light and amenities. Most important factors are traffic, safety, followed by environmental factors, green, shade. Attractiveness and accessibility are key. Other factors mentioned are season of the year, availability of time, education / practice / norms.

Most important factors often are hard to measure, whereas those less important are easier to measure. For example: what is 'safety', how to measure this?

Reprioritizing specifically for particular population groups:

- for elderly new factors were identified such as free public transport, ice-free routes.
- for children as well new factors were identified such as peers, distance from home, sidewalks / bike lanes.
- for women not many changes occurred
- for persons with disabilities: accessibility is most important for this group, as well as safe transport.

Related to part 2:

Measuring green space for primary school aged children. What information would you need? For example, geographical size and detail, at neighbourhood level and/or national level?

Suggestions: adding wearables in order to collect data from children's movements, adding children's voice and perception on good environments. Another presentation was on cycling to work, adding data on private and public land, affordability, subsidized travel information, bicycle storage and seasonal maps. And another idea: "Let's play and move more outside", as children are not getting outside anymore. A variety of public places and increased attractiveness, voice of parents and of children. And plan and measure with the children.

TU Delft proposals:

- children's independent access to greenspace. It is good for children to go outdoors independently; can they reach a (green) space to play without crossing barriers?
- day to day greenspaces. Children go to school every day, but which streets do they pass and how vegetated are those?
- crowd-sourced perceived green spaces. Are data on greenspaces, such as OpenStreetMap and satellite images, complete? Or do they miss greenspaces?

Improvement suggestions: (social) safety of play areas, attractiveness of streets, add children's voice, use of black space and why these are not used (yet).

Presentation on enriching the environmental exposome: road traffic flow prediction and noise modelling (ULEIC)

Road traffic noise re-modelling and including in cohort studies (where needed). European standard modelling method (CNOSSOS-EU) is used to calculate noise exposures at facades of dwellings (and indirectly of individuals) from main roads. In epidemiological studies we need exposure data for smaller/ minor roads, for individual dwellings, and thus this approach according to the Environmental Noise Directive (END) is not ideal. Equal-Life is trying to fill in these gaps by using statistical methods with a selected number of variables (the so-called generalized linear mixed effects regression model). Such as road type, average daily traffic count, population, number of terminal / dead-end roads, nearest major road junction, gradient of the road, connectivity to other road types, number of people that can drive within 5 minutes to a particular location / drivetime. Road traffic flow predictions have been tested in UK, Barcelona; now used for 3D noise modelling.

Questions: What is the influence of electric vehicles? What about low noise emission zones? Dominant source and background noise differ per road type, thus at a residential road you will hear rolling noise whereas at a major road that will be engine noise.

No data on trees (canopies) is included in the modelling. Most challenging is the temporal aspect (and thus data) of road traffic.

Social exposome (NIJZ)

Starting point before the presentation was the description of two main tools for the toolbox/handbook planned from WP 4:

1) For the target group of researchers: Conceptual Framework of the Social Exposome and its implications for research. A brief introduction was given, the conceptual framework is already published (Gudi-Mindermann et al. (2023). Integrating the social environment with an equity perspective into the exposome paradigm: A new conceptual framework of the Social Exposome. Environmental Research. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.116485>).

2) For the target group of policy makers/urban planners/other stakeholders: Logic Model for Equity Impact Assessment and its implications for intervention planning and evaluation. After a brief introduction a Case Study on Noise Legislation in Slovenia was presented.

Explanation of the social exposome conceptual framework, the integration of physical and social exposomes and the health outcomes and health inequalities. To be tested in cohort studies and results expected in / after summer 2024. For the target group of policy makers, urban planners, public health authorities and others is the logic model for equity impact assessment. This is a tool to help embed an equity perspective in the planning, implementation and evaluation process of universal interventions to improve the built environment. Publication foreseen.

Suggestion: include a 'when?' question as well, in addition to How, Who, What and Where.

Case studies conducted in Equal-Life were (i) reduction of environmental noise exposures in Slovenia, (ii) improvement of bicycle infrastructure and increase of cycling behaviour in Macedonia, (iii) mobility hubs and (iv) play areas in Utrecht, the Netherlands. The environmental noise case study is further explained, see the handout / IC BEN conference paper as well.

Discussion on conceptual framework (INCHES)

The aim of this discussion was to get a picture of: (i) what 'type' of information can the different stakeholders apply in their work? (ii) which data or results (exposures, mediators) are relevant to the work of stakeholders? (iii) do stakeholders recognize their own dilemmas and questions that they have in the first results and deviate this from what stakeholders expected, in their work? (e.g. what are the main causes and perhaps mediators for mental health in children, according to the Equal-Life researchers and according to the stakeholders?).

An interactive game was played to get an idea which kind of exposures were prioritized by the stakeholders: physical exposures, mediators or social exposures. In addition, sticky notes were produced. Some outcomes were:

Social exposures were highly rated as being important.

Children's voices need to be and can be heard.

Where is most impact to be expected? In the decision-making systems, there change can be achieved.

Friday 8th September

Case study: City collaboration track, Improving young people's sense of safety in the city (Meri Virta)

Bloomberg and Harvard City Leadership Initiative support, in Helsinki. Public value statement: enabling a safe and welcoming environment for children throughout the day is good for each individual and the community. Tackling the issue by breaking it down into sub causes and identifying complexities by an interdisciplinary team. E.g. lack of safe free time activities for the young, behavioural issues among the young at school and in the streets. Growing number of confrontations between groups, lack of support and sense of belonging for families.

Three entry points have been selected:

- Services are designed for 'average' users
 - o Hobby platform.
 - o Co-create services with children.
 - o New area-based leadership model.
 - o etc.
- Lack of safe free time activities for young
 - o Families have knowledge about free time possibilities for children.
 - o Proactive leisure services find young people without hobbies.
 - o etc.
- Public spaces (incl schools) are experienced as unsafe
 - o Intervening and solving every case of bullying and harassment.
 - o Public space improvements and new school building are prioritized.
 - o Placemaking interventions with children.
 - o etc.

Lessons are integrated into regular work practices.

Problem Driven Interactive Adaptation (PDIA) process (Harvard) steps: Initial problem analysis; Identify action steps; Take action; Check-in; Sustain authority and legitimacy; Adapt and iterate.

Key results and take aways:

- We managed to complete numerous simultaneous joined interventions in the area in matter of months. Initial results indicate that anti social behaviour has decreased in the area.
- Start with the problem and the root causes. Stopping at the common problem was worth the time – this enhanced people's ownership and from an early stage they started seeing their role in the solutions too.
- Make sure you have the right people at the table. Having the mandate to bring about concrete change and interventions was crucial.
- Interventions were based on wide participation of stakeholders and a solid knowledge base.

Qualitative data collection (and use) needs to be improved. Qualitative data will be combined with the existing (quantitative) data in the municipality. Then a decision on form(at) of data collection will be taken.

What happens next?

- Results are compiled and presented to the city leadership. Decisions are yet to be made about scaling.
- All city divisions are committed to strengthening area-based work, utilizing the tools and process trialed in the area.
- Good work continues in the area and similar work will be expanded to the surrounding neighborhoods.
- Key challenge to address: the core group of 8 people put a lot of time into this and received coaching throughout the process – how do we utilize the methods in existing cooperation structures?

Case study: infant mental health (TL- Healthy Cities Cork)

Cork city: Let's grow together! Various interconnected strategies: infant mental health and well-being; speech language communication and literacy.

Early environmental quality: presentation preliminary results (KI)

A combination of birth cohort data and data from school studies.

FAIR cohort: ADHD most important variables (during pregnancy) are birthyear, income, smoking, population density, road intersection closeness, education of father, road distance, etc. For Autism the most important variables are income, green urban areas, build-up area, road noise, green urban area, foreign citizenship, etc. Other results are available from the ALPINE, PIAMA and WALNUTS cohorts.

Question: how to communicate the results?

- Communicate the results per cohort or all pooled cohorts?
- Visualize the importance of the variables. Or a top ten presentation.
- Infographic
- More information is needed, for example on causality, how to interpret the relation between the variable and the outcome.
- Involve stakeholders in reviewing papers! In order to give meaning to research outcomes.

Toolbox and handbook (Quantia)

The stakeholder forum in Helsinki produced beneficial feedback for the revised prototype of the toolbox/handbook. Involvement of stakeholders in broader communication of Equal-Life results is crucial – and offered!

Discussed items for the Toolbox modules are stakeholders, visualization, semantic knowledge exploration, connection and sharing modules. In more detail the Stakeholder module should be an explorative website with clickable elements. Feedback has been tested in previous stakeholder workshops. The updated website is presented in this workshop for comments.

Tools are broadly defined, and a broad selection will be presented, but not hosted on the website but through linkages to the 'owners' of the specific tools. The website will be open for everyone and will have an explorative part.

Use storytelling (workshops) for the researchers in order to collect stories, content for the website.

Suggestions:

- Instead of a website or in addition to the website consider developing an app.
- Link to other websites and dashboards such as UNICEF.

Presentation by LA on Personal listening and IT devices and their relation to lifestyle of adolescents in the Slovak Risk Behavioural Survey

The study is based on a bilateral US-Slovak project to evaluate the impact of selected behavioral, psychological, and socioeconomic factors on adolescent health in the Bratislava agglomeration. Special attention is paid to the use of selected IT devices (TV, PC - personal computers, personal music players - PMPs). The data from 525 students (185 boys) attending 8 secondary schools in Bratislava, aged 15-20 years are presented. The most important health risk behaviors in the students' sample were identified, 90.9 % of students listen to PMP on average for 405 minutes and use mobile phones for 384 minutes per week, significantly more girls. About 50 % of students listen to PMPs more than 200 minutes a week. Those students have a worse lifestyle than those listening to PMPs less than 200 minutes a week. A high percentage of PC usage has been observed, especially during the weekend (72.1% more than three hours per day), and less interest in watching TV. Students use the PC more than their parents and watch less TV, but when watching it, they copy the behavior of both parents. The study presents a challenge for the analysis and for future prevention as well as intervention activities to protect and promote the health of children and youth.

Place Standard Tool for Children and Young People (JH, city of Glasgow)

The Place Standard tool (PSt) was launched in 2015 and in response to on-going feedback a [version for children and young people](#) was co-produced and published in 2022. This tool provides a practical solution to help younger communities identify in a collaborative and inclusive manner what works well within their place, what needs improving and the solutions to address these. The tool is made up of 14 place dimensions which align with the UN SDGs and this relationship coupled with the successful application of the tool across Europe has led to an invitation from WHO to Public Health Scotland (PHS) to host a new Collaborating Centre for Place from 2024 onwards. The lessons learned from the Equal Life Project would be invaluable contribution to the Collaborating Centre's programme.

Equal-Life outcomes and health equity (INCHES)

Interactive session with mentimeter on questions related to data collection and vulnerability. See results in annex 13.

Question 1: There are data collection plans. How can we connect data on physical exposures to knowledge about what works for children's mental health?

Multiple choice answers

- Data Collection and Integration of data
- Interdisciplinary Collaboration
- Longitudinal Studies
- Causal Pathways and Mechanisms
- Community Engagement
- Other

Result: There are data collection plans. How can we connect data on physical exposures to knowledge about what works for children's mental health? Highest rank for 'interdisciplinary collaboration' followed by 'data collection and integration of data'. Suggestion: map data owners and data sources in order to make sense of combinations of data and to make a story on the data.

Related to Vulnerability

The following two questions were based on some homework on a text of vulnerabilities (from WP1).

Question 2: Which dimension of vulnerability do you think will cause most impact on children's mental health? (one answer possible)

- Differential exposure
- Differential susceptibility
- Differentiation in capacity
- Other

Result: Which dimension of vulnerability do you think will cause most impact on children's mental health? Highest ranked answer is 'differential susceptibility'. Alternative answer categories: environmental exposures and preventive interventions.

Note: the used terms are quite difficult to understand.

Question 3: Which dimension of vulnerability provides the best opportunity for policy action?

(one answer possible)

- Differential exposure
- Differential susceptibility
- Differentiation in capacity
- Other

Result: Highest ranking answer is 'differential exposures'.

The final question was related to Transdisciplinary interaction.

Improving transdisciplinary cooperation in policy development requires a thoughtful and strategic approach to breaking down silos, fostering collaboration, and integrating diverse perspectives. Transdisciplinary cooperation involves working across multiple disciplines and stakeholders to address complex issues and create well-rounded policies.

Question 4

Which approach will enhance transdisciplinary interaction in your view most?

Multiple choice answers (more answers possible),

- Shared Vision and Goals
- Diverse Stakeholder Engagement
- Effective Communication
- Interdisciplinary Training
- Integrated Research and Data Sharing
- Other

Result: Highest ranking answer is 'effective communication', followed by 'diverse stakeholder engagement' and 'interdisciplinary training'.

Wrap-up and conclusions (INCHES and CoU)

Actions and next steps:

- Stakeholder review in analyses and reporting
- Broadening participation / stakeholder engagement from various disciplines
- Policy recommendations
- Story telling
- Social media plan / dissemination plan
- Training
- Next meeting to be scheduled: early June 2024, possible locations Cork, Ghent or Leipzig

In conclusion: The collaborative efforts within Work Package 8 (WP8 together with WP9) have yielded substantial progress in shaping and developing ideas for policy development, the toolbox and guidebook. Each task was executed in a synergistic manner, resulting in a prototype of the semantic exploration and knowledge tools that was presented to stakeholders in Helsinki. This, alongside active participation in stakeholder workshops and joint endeavors with WP9, bolstered stakeholder engagement and enriched project resources.

Co-design process

Co-design is a design-led process that uses creative and participatory methods. There is no onsize-fits-all approach. Instead, there are patterns and principles that can be applied in different ways with different people. Importantly, co-designers make decisions, not just suggestions ([Burkett, 2012](#))

Source: <https://www.yacwa.org.au/wpcontent/uploads/2016/09/An-Introduction-to-Co-Design-by-Ingrid-Burkett.pdf>

Design thinking

- Context analysis
 - Stakeholder segmentation
 - Wishes
 - Aims
 - Position
 - Influence
 - Personas
 - Behaviour
 - Attitude
 - Missing partners

<https://g8mvf9i2x72.typeform.com/to/K6PpU2xZ?typeformsource=www.linkedin.com>

Design thinking

3 phases

- Empathize - understand and share the feelings of another
- Define - to determine or identify the essential qualities or meaning of whatever defines the problem
- Ideate - a creative process where designers generate ideas in sessions

DESIGN THINKING: A NON-LINEAR PROCESS

Principles of co-design

Annex 12 Working on application of tools

Different design and participation approaches, focusing on where power is held and in whose interests it is exercised.

These things are transactional at best, harmful, degrading and violent at worst		
Approach	Keywords	Where power is held
Designing at people	Designer, professional or policy-maker as expert, top-down decision-making	<i>Designing at people</i> is about what decision-makers and designers think and want.
Designing for people	Design thinking, anything 'centred' e.g. human-centred (HCD), user-centred (UCD), patient-centred, citizen-centred design etc.	<i>Designing for people</i> is about what designers and decision-makers want to know and achieve. Good intent usually ends up as system-centred, designer-centred, executive-centred or staff-centred by implementation.
These things are transformational at best, however they are not inherently inclusive or equitable		
Designing with people and planet	Co-design, participatory design, deliberative democracy	<i>Designing with people</i> is about what matters to people with lived experience and decision-makers (co-decided).
Led by the people	Co-production, community-led design, citizen movements, design justice*	<i>Led by the people</i> is about what people, families and communities want for themselves.

Kelly Ann McKercher, 2020

What is the 'social movement' part of co -design?

To make co -design a reality, we need systems, organisations and communities to embrace the leadership and contributions of people with lived experience. Doing that requires different ways of thinking and being, which are missing from many teams, organisations and systems. The table below describes several social movements that are necessary to make co -design a reality and a norm.

Social movement aspects of co-design

From	To
Making decisions for people with lived experience	Making decisions with people with lived experience
Valuing professional expertise above all	Valuing professional and lived experience equally
Seeing marginalised people as a burden	Seeing marginalised people as resilient, creative and capable
Colonising, heteronormative and ableist systems	Compassionate systems that see and respond to dimensions of difference
Believing that resources are scarce to make change	Seeing an abundance of experience, ideas and energy for change
Focusing on 'consumer' councils and committees	Embedding participation in everyday practice
Rushing to solutions	Slowing down to listen, connect and learn

McKercher, K. A. (2020). *Beyond Sticky Notes. Doing Co-design for real: mindsets, methods and movements.*

Process

Building the conditions

.... Through focusing on relationships, widening inclusion and offering genuine invitation that encourage people to share their strengths

Develop frameworks for safety

.....e.g. frameworks for serious disclosure, safe disclosure, frameworks for recognition, attribution and payment (compensate/pay your co-designers)

There are data collection plans. How can we connect data on physical exposures to knowledge about what works for children’s mental health?

Which dimension of vulnerability do you think will cause most impact on children's mental health?

Which dimension of vulnerability provides the best opportunity for policy action?

Which approach will enhance transdisciplinary interaction in your view most?

Annex 14 research questions used in Como co-design workshop

Research questions

Session 3. Topic: **Research questions**

The aim of this session is focus on the use of our research results to the world of policymaking.

Therefore, we would like to ask you to do some homework before the meeting in Como.

We have a range of research questions.

Table 1 shows an overview of external exposome questions in association with cognitive and mental health outcomes. These are overarching research questions.

Table 2 shows the outline for a list of questions focusing on a combination of selected exposures (external and internal). These questions are also anticipated as overarching research questions. In this list of questions, there are 7 core questions which are then repeated for the 9 different outcomes that are of interest in Equal-Life. These targeted questions aim to consider both the cumulative effects and the life-course perspective in analysing the effects of different combinations of exposures on mental health and cognitive outcomes. The targeted analysis will also include mediators, modifiers and re-reversed causality (bi-directional) analyses.

In addition to the main research questions in Equal-Life, in Table 3, we have gathered questions that are specific to studying the associations between diverse types of exposomes (e.g., social exposome, physical exposome).

As homework we would like to ask you to choose for each table the three questions that you consider the most relevant.

You may have specific criteria that support your decision. Please take note of your arguments to select your preference questions.

You might consider arguments based on feasibility to make interventions, on the biggest health impact, on cost-benefit reasons, on supporting current projects, or any other reason. You also have arguments why some research questions are not good, not feasible or maybe not just or ethical.

Do you consider research questions as such are valuable for stakeholders like policy makers or only the results?

Can you bring your filled in forms to Como.

However, we prefer it if you could send us your filled in forms two days before so we can print them out.

In the session related to the Equal-Life questions we will discuss your feedback on the research questions.

Table 1. Research questions on the overarching external exposome

Question #	Research question	Exposure	Outcome	Time windows of exposure	Time windows of outcome
1	Which exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings are associated with nonverbal IQ?	External exposome (physical + social)	Non-verbal IQ (including attention, working memory, short- and long-term memory, and executive functions)	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
2	Which exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings are associated with the Language development?	External exposome (physical + social)	Language development (including Verbal-IQ, dyslexia, and verbal and reading comprehension)	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
3	Which exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings are associated with grades?	External exposome (physical + social)	School achievement (including grades and, arithmetic and language tests)	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	7-12, adolescence (might change between countries)
4	Which exposures in residential and pre-school settings are associated with motor skills?	External exposome (physical + social)	Motor skills	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2	0-2, 3-6, (7-12, adolescence)
5	Which exposures in residential, pre-school and school setting are associated with Well-being?	External exposome (physical + social)	Well-being (including life satisfaction, quality of life. etc.)	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	4-6, 7-12, adolescence

6	Which exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings are associated with Internalizing symptoms?	External exposome (physical + social)	Internalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). Anxiety, Depression, and Eating disorder (as diagnosis)	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Depression/anxiety: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
7	Which exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings are associated with Externalizing Symptoms?	External exposome (physical + social)	Externalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). ADHD and Conduct disorders (as diagnosis)	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis ADHD: 6-12 Diagnosis Conduct D: 5-6, 7-12, adolescence
8	Which exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings are associated with Thought disorders?	External exposome (physical + social)	Thought disorders (measured by psychometric tests). Autism (as diagnosis)	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Autism: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
9	Which exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings are associated with the p-factor?	External exposome (physical + social)	p-factor (index-variables)	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, 13-16	3-6, 7-12, 13-16
10	Which exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings during a child's life are associated with internal biomarkers of mental health and what time windows are most important?	External exposome (physical + social)	Internal biomarkers of mental health	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence

Table 2. Research questions on selected list of exposures (social and/or physical) and outcomes of interest to Equal-Life.

Question #	Research question	Exposure	Outcome	Mediator	Time windows of exposure	Time windows of outcome
11	How are exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings associated with nonverbal IQ?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Non-verbal IQ (including attention, working memory, short- and long-term memory, and executive functions)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
11a	How does the irregularity, unpredictability, and duration of social and physical risk factors affect Non-verbal IQ in children across their life-course?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Non-verbal IQ (including attention, working memory, short- and long-term memory, and executive functions)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
11b	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical indoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on non-verbal IQ later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Non-verbal IQ (including attention, working memory, short- and long-term memory, and executive functions)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence

11c	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical outdoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on non-verbal IQ later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or Physical exposome	Non-verbal IQ (including attention, working memory, short- and long-term memory, and executive functions)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
11d	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do social exposures moderate the effect of physical exposures on the child's non-verbal IQ outcomes?	Physical exposome	Non-verbal IQ (including attention, working memory, short- and long-term memory, and executive functions)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
11e	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do physical exposures moderate the effect of social exposures on the child's non-verbal IQ outcomes?	Social exposome	Non-verbal IQ (including attention, working memory, short- and long-term memory, and executive functions)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
11f	Does growing up in a supportive social environment modify the negative effects of physical environment on the child's non-verbal IQ?	Selected list of exposure indicators from physical exposome	Non-verbal IQ (including attention, working memory, short- and long-term memory, and executive functions)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence

12	How are exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings associated with language development?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Language development (including Verbal-IQ, dyslexia, and verbal and reading comprehension)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
12a	How does the <i>irregularity, unpredictability, and duration</i> of social and physical risk factors affect language development in children across their life-course?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Language development (including Verbal-IQ, dyslexia, and verbal and reading comprehension)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
12b	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical indoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on language development later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Language development (including Verbal-IQ, dyslexia, and verbal and reading comprehension)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
12c	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical outdoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on language development later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Language development (including Verbal-IQ, dyslexia, and verbal and reading comprehension)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence

12d	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do social exposures moderate the effect of physical exposures on the child's language development?	Physical exposome	Language development (including Verbal-IQ, dyslexia, and verbal and reading comprehension)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
12e	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do physical exposures moderate the effect of social exposures on the child's language development?	Social exposome	Language development (including Verbal-IQ, dyslexia, and verbal and reading comprehension)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
12f	Does growing up in a supportive social environment modify the negative effects of physical environment on the child's language development?	Selected list of exposure indicators from physical exposome	Language development (including Verbal-IQ, dyslexia, and verbal and reading comprehension)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
13	How are exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings associated with school achievement?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	School achievement (including grades and, arithmetic and language tests)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	7-12, adolescence (might change between countries)

13a	How does the <i>irregularity, unpredictability, and duration</i> of social and physical risk factors affect school achievement in children across their life-course?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	School achievement (including grades and, arithmetic and language tests)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	7-12, adolescence (might change between countries)
13b	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical indoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on school achievement later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	School achievement (including grades and, arithmetic and language tests)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	7-12, adolescence (might change between countries)
13c	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical outdoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on school achievement later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	School achievement (including grades and, arithmetic and language tests)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	7-12, adolescence (might change between countries)

13d	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do social exposures moderate the effect of physical exposures on the child's school achievement?	Physical exposome	School achievement (including grades and, arithmetic and language tests)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	7-12, adolescence (might change between countries)
13e	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do physical exposures moderate the effect of social exposures on the child's school achievement?	Social exposome	School achievement (including grades and, arithmetic and language tests)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	7-12, adolescence (might change between countries)
13f	Does growing up in a supportive social environment modify the negative effects of physical environment on the child's school achievement?	Selected list of exposure indicators from physical exposome	School achievement (including grades and, arithmetic and language tests)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	7-12, adolescence (might change between countries)
14	How are exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings associated with motor skills?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Motor skills	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, (7-12, adolescence)

14a	How does the <i>irregularity, unpredictability, and duration</i> of social and physical risk factors affect motor skills in children across their life-course?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Motor skills	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, (7-12, adolescence)
14b	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical indoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on motor skills later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Motor skills	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	0-2, 3-6, (7-12, adolescence)
14c	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical outdoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on motor skills later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Motor skills	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	0-2, 3-6, (7-12, adolescence)

14d	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do social exposures moderate the effect of physical exposures on the child's motor skills?	Physical exposome	Motor skills	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, (7-12, adolescence)
14e	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do physical exposures moderate the effect of social exposures on the child's motor skills?	Social exposome	Motor skills	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, (7-12, adolescence)
14f	Does growing up in a supportive social environment modify the negative effects of physical environment on the child's motor skills?	Selected list of exposure indicators from physical exposome	Motor skills	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, (7-12, adolescence)
15	How are exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings associated with well-being?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Well-being (including quality of life, eudonic well-being and hedonic well-being))	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	4-6, 7-12, adolescence

15a	How does the <i>irregularity, unpredictability, and duration</i> of social and physical risk factors affect well-being in children across their life-course?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Well-being (including quality of life, eudonic well-being and hedonic well-being)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	4-6, 7-12, adolescence
15b	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical indoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on well-being later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Well-being (including quality of life, eudonic well-being and hedonic well-being)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	4-6, 7-12, adolescence
15c	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical outdoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on well-being later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Well-being (including: quality of life, eudonic well-being and hedonic well-being)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	4-6, 7-12, adolescence

15d	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do social exposures moderate the effect of physical exposures on the child's well-being?	Physical exposome	Well-being (including: quality of life, eudonic well-being and hedonic well-being)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	4-6, 7-12, adolescence
15e	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do physical exposures moderate the effect of social exposures on the child's well-being?	Social exposome	Well-being (including: quality of life, eudonic well-being and hedonic well-being)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	4-6, 7-12, adolescence
15f	Does growing up in a supportive social environment modify the negative effects of physical environment on the child's well-being?	Selected list of exposure indicators from physical exposome	Well-being (including: quality of life, eudonic well-being and hedonic well-being)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	4-6, 7-12, adolescence
16	How are exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings associated with Internalizing behaviours?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Internalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). Anxiety, Depression, and Eating disorder (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Depression/anxiety: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence

16a	How does the <i>irregularity, unpredictability, and duration</i> of social and physical risk factors affect internalizing behaviours in children across their life-course?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Internalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). Anxiety, Depression, and Eating disorder (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Depression/anxiety: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
16b	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical indoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on internalizing behaviours later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Internalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). Anxiety, Depression, and Eating disorder (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Depression/anxiety: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
16c	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical outdoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on internalizing behaviours later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Internalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). Anxiety, Depression, and Eating disorder (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Depression/anxiety: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence

16d	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do social exposures moderate the effect of physical exposures on the child's internalizing behaviours?	Physical exposome	Internalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). Anxiety, Depression, and Eating disorder (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Depression/anxiety: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
16e	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do physical exposures moderate the effect of social exposures on the child's internalizing behaviors?	Social exposome	Internalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). Anxiety, Depression, and Eating disorder (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Depression/anxiety: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
16f	Does growing up in a supportive social environment modify the negative effects of physical environment on the child's internalizing behaviors?	Selected list of exposure indicators from physical exposome	Internalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). Anxiety, Depression, and Eating disorder (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Depression/anxiety: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
17	How are exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings associated with externalizing behaviors?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Externalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). ADHD and Conduct disorders (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis ADHD: 6-12 Diagnosis Conduct D: 5-6, 7-12, adolescence

17a	How does the <i>irregularity, unpredictability, and duration</i> of social and physical risk factors affect externalizing behaviors in children across their life-course?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Externalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). ADHD and Conduct disorders (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis ADHD: 6-12 Diagnosis Conduct D: 5-6, 7-12, adolescence
17b	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical indoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on externalizing behaviors later in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Externalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). ADHD and Conduct disorders (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis ADHD: 6-12 Diagnosis Conduct D: 5-6, 7-12, adolescence
17c	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical outdoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on externalizing behaviors later in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Externalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). ADHD and Conduct disorders (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis ADHD: 6-12 Diagnosis Conduct D: 5-6, 7-12, adolescence

17d	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do social exposures moderate the effect of physical exposures on the child's externalizing behaviors?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Externalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). ADHD and Conduct disorders (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis ADHD: 6-12 Diagnosis Conduct D: 5-6, 7-12, adolescence
17e	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do physical exposures moderate the effect of social exposures on the child's externalizing behaviors?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Externalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). ADHD and Conduct disorders (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis ADHD: 6-12 Diagnosis Conduct D: 5-6, 7-12, adolescence
17f	Does growing up in a supportive social environment modify the negative effects of physical environment on the child's externalizing behaviors?	Selected list of exposure indicators from physical exposome	Externalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). ADHD and Conduct disorders (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis ADHD: 6-12 Diagnosis Conduct D: 5-6, 7-12, adolescence
18	How are exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings associated with Thought disorders?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Thought disorders (measured by psychometric tests). Autism (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Autism: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence

18a	How does the <i>irregularity, unpredictability, and duration</i> of social and physical risk factors affect thought disorders in children across their life-course?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Thought disorders (measured by psychometric tests). Autism (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Autism: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
18b	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical indoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on thought disorders later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Thought disorders (measured by psychometric tests). Autism (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Autism: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
18c	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical indoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on thought disorders later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Thought disorders (measured by psychometric tests). Autism (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Autism: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence

18d	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do social exposures moderate the effect of physical exposures on the child's thought disorders?	Physical exposome	Thought disorders (measured by psychometric tests). Autism (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Autism: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
18e	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do physical exposures moderate the effect of social exposures on the child's thought disorders?	Social exposome	Thought disorders (measured by psychometric tests). Autism (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Autism: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
18f	Does growing up in a supportive social environment modify the negative effects of physical environment on the child's thought disorders?	Selected list of exposure indicators from physical exposome	Thought disorders (measured by psychometric tests). Autism (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Autism: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
19	How are exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings associated with p-factor?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	p-factor (index-variables)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	3-6, 7-12, 13-16

19a	How does the irregularity, unpredictability, and duration of social and physical risk factors affect p-factor values in children across their life-course?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	p-factor (index-variables)	Sleep/stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	3-6, 7-12, 13-16
19b	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical indoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on p-factor later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	p-factor (index-variables)	Sleep/stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	3-6, 7-12, 13-16
19c	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical <i>out-door</i> environment and social exposome in early life stage on p-factor later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	p-factor (index-variables)	Sleep/stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	3-6, 7-12, 13-16

19d	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do social exposures moderate the effect of physical exposures on the child's p-factor outcomes?	Physical exposome	p-factor (index-variables)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	3-6, 7-12, 13-16
19e	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do physical exposures moderate the effect of social exposures on the child's p-factor outcomes?	Social exposome	p-factor (index-variables)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	3-6, 7-12, 13-16
19f	Does growing up in a supportive social environment modify the negative effects of physical environment on the child's p-factor outcomes?	Selected list of exposure indicators from physical exposome	p-factor (index-variables)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	3-6, 7-12, 13-16
20	How are exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings associated with biomarkers of mental health (identified by WP2)?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Biomarkers of mental health	-	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence

20a	How do internal biomarkers mediate the pathway from physical and social exposures in early life to mental health and cognitive outcomes?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Different outcomes identified in Equal-Life	Internal exposome (biomarkers of mental health)	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
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Table 3. Research questions on associations between social and physical exposome

No	Research question	Exposures
21	Are there subgroups of children that follow different exposome paths over life?	Critical life events, socio-economic status, migrant background, area of residence (urban/rural), gender, etc.
22	What cumulative measures (scores) for external exposome can be made? a) what parts of exposome are stable over time b) what parts of exposome are highly correlated	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome
23	Are built environmental factors merely spatially correlated or do some mediate the effect of others?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome that relate to the built environment, such as population density, greenspace, noise, air pollution, street connectivity
24	How does a child's perspective of exposures differ from an adult's perspective?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome
25	How do individual and combined exposure patterns change over a child's life course?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome
26	How do social exposures determine variation in physical exposures? (exposure differential)	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome

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| 27 | How do physical exposures determine the variation in social exposures? | Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome |
| 28 | Development of new exposure assessment models and indicators and comparison of exposure metrics obtained from different sources | Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome |

i. David Elkind, *the Power of Play*, Lifelong books 2007

ii. James Bowlby, *Attachment*, New York: Basic Books 1969

iii. Rutger Bergman, *Utopia for Realist*, de Correspondent 2014